

ECHoS

Cancer Mission Hubs

**Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement
(PPIE) in Cancer Policy and Governance: Exploring
Current Practices in Public Administration**

www.cancermissionhubs.eu

Funded by
the European Union

DOCUMENT CONTROL	
Document name	MS14 – Maturity Map
Work Package	WP6 - Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) in Cancer Policy and Governance: Exploring Current Practices in Public Administration
Dissemination level	Public
Revision	0.5
Status (draft, final)	Final
Project Officer	Ioannis Vouldis (HaDEA)
Authors	Anita Gottlob-Leitner, Barbara Fröschl, Daniela Rojatz, Isabella Schiller
Reviewers	José Salvado, Hugo Soares, Yasmin Fonseca (AICIB); Dina Dabaghie and Eva Jolie (KCCC)
Beneficiary(ies)	GÖG
Keywords	PPIE, Public Administration, Cancer

Dissemination level: PU = Public, for wide dissemination (public deliverables shall be of a professional standard in a form suitable for print or electronic publication) or CO = Confidential, limited to project participants and European Commission.

REVISION HISTORY				
Revision	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
0.1	03.03.2026	Anita Gottlob-Leitner, Barbara Fröschl, Daniela Rojatz, Isabella Schiller	GÖG	First draft has been internally reviewed and submitted by GÖG
0.2	12.03.2026	José Salvado, Hugo Soares	AICIB	WP6 Review & EB Review
0.3	17.03.2026	Dina Dabaghie and Eva Jolie	KCCC	WP6 Review & EB Review
0.4	01.04.2026	Anita Gottlob-Leitner, Barbara Fröschl, Daniela Rojatz, Isabella Schiller	GÖG	Final version
0.5	09.04.2026	Yasmin Fonseca	AICIB	Quality review

Disclaimer:

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme. Grant Agreement N°: 101104587. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of contents

Tables	5
Figures.....	5
Acknowledgements/Contributions	6
Abbreviations.....	7
Introduction.....	9
Prior work.....	11
Working Definition of PPIE	11
Methodology	12
Survey Design	12
Survey Tool.....	14
Selection of experts.....	14
Mode of Distribution.....	14
Analysis.....	15
Patient Organisation Perspectives.....	15
Limitations	16
Results.....	18
Strengthen Public Sector Capacities (Area 1A)	21
Patient and Public Involvement in National Cancer Control Plans (Area 1B).	26
Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion (Area 2)	28
Participation Influences Transparent Decisions (Area 3).....	31
Active Mechanisms in Policy/Legislation Development (Area 4)	32
Adequate and Sustainable Resources (Area 5).....	34
Civil Society Capacity Strengthening (Area 6).....	38
Monitoring and Evaluation (Area 7).....	41
Integrated Heatmap.....	44
Results from Patient Organisation Perspectives.....	46
Reflections on public administration responses	46
Facilitators and barriers to meaningful PPIE according to Patient Organisation responses.....	47
Learnings & Discussion	53

Strengthen Public Sector Capacities (Area 1A and 1B)	53
Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion (Area 2)	55
Participation Influences Transparent Decisions (Area 3).....	56
Active Mechanisms in Policy/Legislation Development (Area 4).....	57
Adequate and Sustainable Resources (Area 5).....	58
Civil Society Capacity Strengthening (Area 6).....	59
Monitoring and Evaluation (Area 7)	60
Conclusion and Key Recommendations.....	61
References	66
ANNEX – Completed Survey responses.....	67
Survey Template.....	67
Austria	76
Belgium	85
Croatia.....	92
Cyprus.....	101
Finland.....	108
Germany.....	115
Hungary.....	124
Ireland.....	132
Italy.....	141
The Netherlands.....	149
Norway.....	160
Portugal.....	167
Romania	176
Slovakia	183
Sweden.....	191
Turkey.....	201

Tables

Table 1. Development of thematic survey areas.....	13
Table 2. Participating organisation.....	18
Table 3. Key Recommendations in Context.....	62

Figures

Figure 1. Importance of patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development in public administration.	21
Figure 2. Confirmed funding for training programmes.....	22
Figure 3. Stages of PPIE across the oncology policy cycle (% of countries).....	24
Figure 4. Type of patient and/or citizen representatives involved in implementing the NCCP (% of countries)	28
Figure 5. Accessibility measures used in PPIE activities within public administration frameworks (% of countries).....	29
Figure 6. Forms in which consultation outcomes are shared among participating countries (% of countries)	32
Figure 7. Heatmap on the extent of involvement of patients and the public in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (sorted by average scores, scores range from 1 to 5).....	34
Figure 8. Mapping of public sector resources allocated to support effective PPIE in oncology activities (countries sorted alphabetically)	35
Figure 9. Extent of capacity building initiatives (training, technical support, funding schemes) for patient and civil society participation	39
Figure 10. Country practices in tracking PPIE inked outcome indicators (countries sorted alphabetically).....	42
Figure 11. Heatmap on implementation levels of PPIE in cancer policy and governance.....	45

Acknowledgements/Contributions

Countries	Number of organisations as part of the ECHO S Consortium	Number of organisations external to ECHO S
Austria	1	2
Belgium	1	1
Croatia		1
Cyprus	1	1
Finland		
Germany		1
Hungary		1
Ireland	1	
Italy	1	
the Netherlands		2
Norway	1	
Portugal	1	
Romania	1	
Slovakia	1	
Sweden		2
Turkey		1

Abbreviations

AICIB	Agency for Clinical Research and Biomedical Innovation
AMPEU	National Agency for Mobility and EU Programmes
APEnet	Associazione Rete italiana degli Atenei ed Enti di Ricerca per il Public Engagement
BAG	Bundesarbeitsgemeinschaft
BMSGPK	Bundesministerium für Soziales, Gesundheit, Pflege und Konsumentenschutz
CCRI	Cyprus Cancer Research Institute
ECHO S	Establishing of Cancer Mission Hubs: Networks and Synergies
ECIS	European Cancer Information System
EU	European Union
EUPATI	European Patients' Academy on Therapeutic Innovation
FICAN	Finish Cancer Centre
FRRB	Fondazione Regionale per la Ricerca Biomedica
G-BA	Gemeinsamer Bundesausschuss
GÖG	Gesundheit Österreich GmbH (Austrian National Public Health Institute)
HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HCP	Health Care Professional
HZJZ	Hrvatski zavod za javno zdravstvo
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
INOMED	Centre for Innovation in Medicine

LBG	Ludwig Boltzmann Gesellschaft
MoH	Ministry of Health
MS	Milestone
NCI	National Cancer Institute
NCCP	National Cancer Control Plan
NCMH	National Cancer Mission Hubs
NFK	Nederlandse Federatie van Kankerpatiëntenorganisaties
NKC	Nederlands Kanker Collectief
NOISK	Národný onkologický inštitút Slovenska
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
OKFŐ	Országos Korhazai Foglalkoztatás
ÖKUSS	Österreichische Kompetenz- und Servicestelle für Selbsthilfe
PPIE	Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement
PREM	Patient Reported Experience Measure
PROM	Patient Reported Outcome Measure
RCC	Regional Cancer Centre
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
UCY	University of Cyprus
UN	United Nations
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work package

Introduction

Cancer remains one of the most significant public health challenges in Europe. In 2024, an estimated 2.7 million new cancer cases and 1.3 million cancer deaths were recorded across the European Union, and although both incidence and mortality have shown modest declines in recent years, cancer continues to place a substantial burden on health systems and societies (1, 2). Despite advances in prevention, early detection, and treatment, persistent inequalities in cancer incidence, mortality, and access to care across European countries further highlight the need for governance approaches that ensure health systems respond effectively to the needs, experiences, and priorities of patients and citizens.

Across Europe, citizen and patient involvement and engagement (PPIE) has therefore become a central principle of people-centred and equitable health systems. Public health governance literature demonstrates that meaningful participation contributes to improved legitimacy, accountability, responsiveness, and quality of policy decisions (1, 3-5). In oncology specifically, patient engagement has increasingly been recognised as essential across the cancer continuum — from prevention and screening to treatment, survivorship, and research prioritisation — supporting more responsive care pathways and improved alignment between health services and patient needs (6, 7)).

At the European level, the EU Mission on Cancer places citizens and patients at the centre of research, innovation, and policy development. Its implementation framework emphasises structured and meaningful engagement to ensure that citizens' and patients' perspectives actively shape prevention strategies, screening programmes, treatment pathways, and survivorship policies (8). The Mission approach and related initiatives and projects such as ECHO S, reflect a broader shift towards collaborative models, including Penta Helix approaches that promote interaction between public authorities, research institutions, healthcare providers, industry, and civil society. Within this framework, National Cancer Mission Hubs (NCMHs) are expected to play a central role in strengthening stakeholder participation and facilitating coordinated action at national level.

International policy frameworks further reinforce the importance of institutionalised participation. The World Health Organization's (WHO) framework on people-centred health services and its resolution on social participation for universal health coverage call for the systematic inclusion of people's voices across the policy cycle — from agenda-setting to monitoring and evaluation — as a core

element of resilient and accountable health systems (5, 9). Similarly, the OECD emphasises that structured citizen participation can strengthen public governance, improve policy effectiveness, and enhance trust in public institutions (10).

Despite this strong normative emphasis, structured and comparable evidence on how patient and citizen engagement is institutionalised within public administration remains limited, especially in cancer governance. While engagement initiatives are increasingly documented in clinical settings, research projects, and civil society-led activities, there is comparatively little systematic evidence on how participation mechanisms are embedded within ministries, national cancer control programme (NCCP) structures, cancer agencies, regulatory bodies, or other public authorities.

Addressing this knowledge gap is particularly important in the context of developing and supporting NCMHs. These hubs offer a strategically advantageous starting point for embedding robust participatory governance structures from the outset and for systematically integrating the required involvement of patients and citizens. Without a clearer understanding of how engagement mechanisms are institutionalised within public administration, initiatives to expand, harmonise, or build participation capacities risk remaining fragmented and unevenly implemented. As a necessary first step, a structured overview of existing participation practices and the relevant regulatory and organisational frameworks is therefore essential.

Against this background, the objective for the work described here was generating comparable cross-country data on the institutionalisation of PPIE within public administration structures – with a special emphasis across countries participating in the ECHO S project. Drawing on a structured expert survey complemented by qualitative reflections from patient organisations, the study provides a comparative maturity mapping of governance arrangements, institutional capacities, and participation mechanisms. Results identify common patterns, variations, and capacity gaps and inform recommendations to strengthen meaningful and sustainable engagement in oncology policy and programme development.

The overall purpose of this analysis is to generate a first explorative overview on the institutionalisation of PPIE within the public administration sector across participating partner countries to facilitate:

- 1) the development of further capacity building work on PPIE in cancer and in future ECHO S activities
- 2) the strengthening of PPIE practices within the context of National Cancer Mission Hubs and
- 3) providing an evidence base for policy recommendations related to PPIE in cancer actions – including policy and governance.

Prior work

This analysis builds directly on ECHO S Milestone 13 (Landscape Analysis), which mapped citizen engagement activities across the five sectors of the Penta helix model (public administration, academia, industry, health and care, and patients and citizens). While the landscape analysis provided a broad overview of existing activities across sectors, it did not assess the depth, institutionalisation, or governance anchoring of engagement mechanisms within individual sectors. Given that consistent and sustainable PPIE are in part shaped through structural framework conditions, including legislation, governance, and funding the present milestone therefore adopts a more focused approach by examining one sector — public administration — in greater depth.

Working Definition of PPIE

For the purposes of this analysis, PPIE in cancer governance is defined as the regular, meaningful and well-resourced involvement of patients, survivors, carers and the public in the design, decision-making, implementation and evaluation of policies, programmes and services across the cancer continuum. The scope of this maturity map is therefore limited to national and regional governance and administrative bodies — including ministries of health, NCCP bodies, cancer agencies, and relevant regulatory or payer institutions where applicable. Individual clinical encounters and single-institution quality improvement initiatives without policy relevance are outside the scope of this analysis.

Methodology

This analysis applies a structured yet qualitative expert-based data collection approach, complemented by qualitative input from umbrella patient organisations. The methodological design was guided by the objective of generating comparable cross-country data on the institutionalisation of PPIE within public administration structures. The initial part of the survey included a short introduction text that specifying the objectives, target respondents, as well as the working definition of PPIE used throughout the survey.

For this work, elements of mixed-method research standards for survey design and reporting were applied (11), while allowing methodological flexibility appropriate to the exploratory nature of the study.

Given the limited availability of standardised datasets capturing governance arrangements related to PPIE, expert surveys represent an established and appropriate method in contexts where institutional practices require contextual interpretation, particularly in governance and health systems research. This approach enables the systematic collection of informed assessments from individuals with direct knowledge of national cancer governance structures.

Survey Design

The survey instrument was developed through an iterative process involving internal review and expert validation. Draft questions and operationalised indicators were discussed and refined during several ECHO S Work Package 6 (WP6) meetings between June and August 2025. In addition, a dedicated workshop with ECHO S partners possessing extensive survey expertise was conducted in August 2025 to review the structure, clarity, and relevance of the questionnaire. The final set of indicators was operationalised into a structured survey template and implemented using the [LimeSurvey](#) platform version 6.16.8+260209.

Indicator Development

The development of the indicator framework followed a two-step conceptual process.

First, the WHO Resolution on Social Participation for Universal Health Coverage (9) was used as the primary normative reference framework. The resolution outlines seven key recommendation areas addressing the institutionalisation of social participation within health governance systems. These areas provided the conceptual backbone for the present analysis.

Second, the resolution’s seven areas were translated and operationalised into **indicators specifically tailored to the field of cancer policy and governance**. This adaptation process ensured that the indicators:

- Reflect the realities of national cancer governance structures,
- Align with the objectives of the EU Mission on Cancer, and
- Generate findings that can directly inform NCMHs and the further development of self-assessment tools in future ECHO S resources.

Table 1 shows how developed indicators loosely relate to the WHO resolution areas. The Survey template including all questions and answer options is attached in the **ANNEX**, at the end of this report, also including a more detailed description of each survey Area.

Table 1. Development of thematic survey areas

WHO Resolution Recommendation Areas (WHO, 2024)	Milestone 14 Survey indicators
1. Strengthen public-sector capacities	Area 1 A - Strengthen public sector capacities Area 1 B - National Cancer Control Plans
2. Enable equitable, diverse and inclusive participation	Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion
3. Ensure participation influences transparent decisions across the policy cycle	Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions

4. Implement & sustain regular participation via mechanisms in policy/legislation	Area 4 - Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development
5. Allocate adequate & sustainable resources	Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources
6. Build civil-society capacity	Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening
7. Support research, pilots, monitoring & evaluation	Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation

Survey Tool

The survey was administered using [LimeSurvey](#), a web-based application for the design and management of online surveys. The Austrian National Public Health Institute (GÖG) provided access to the platform through its institutional license. LimeSurvey was selected due to its flexibility in implementing structured questionnaires and its suitability for secure web-based data collection.

Selection of experts

Public administration experts were nominated by ECHO S Consortium members for each participating country and selected based on their expertise in cancer governance, public administration structures, and national policy frameworks. The nomination period ran from August to November 2025, during which multiple reminders were sent to ECHO S Consortium members to support submissions.

Mode of Distribution

The survey was distributed via email to nominated country experts. Each invitation included a personalised survey link, a PDF version of the questionnaire for reference, and information outlining the scope of the study, the intended timeline, and contact details for follow-up questions. Recipients were asked to confirm their availability and willingness to participate.

Given the gradual nomination of contacts and a lower-than-anticipated response rate, several reminder emails were sent to each nominated expert with the final deadline for submission in January 2026.

Analysis

Survey responses of the expert survey were reviewed for completeness, internal consistency, and comparability across countries. Where necessary, follow-up clarification was sought from respondents to address ambiguities and ensure consistent interpretation of responses.

The data were analysed using a descriptive and thematic approach. Responses were aggregated at the level of predefined thematic categories corresponding to the survey areas (see Table 1), allowing for the identification of patterns in the institutionalisation of PPIE within public administration structures across countries.

Results are presented at the level of thematic areas, with illustrative country examples provided where relevant to highlight different governance arrangements and implementation practices. Where responses to specific survey items were incomplete or missing, the sample size (n) was adjusted to reflect the number of valid responses per question.

Patient Organisation Perspectives

Alongside the nomination process for public administration experts, ECHO S Consortium members were also asked to nominate two patient organisation representatives for each country, ideally from umbrella organisations.

Following the analysis of the survey results, nominated patient organisation representatives were contacted via email and invited to provide input. Each organisation received an overview of the survey responses relating to their country, presented in anonymised form without identifying the public administration respondent. This approach enabled patient organisations to reflect on the findings from an external stakeholder perspective.

Patient organisation representatives were further asked to respond to three guiding questions: (1) facilitators — what currently enables meaningful patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) in oncology policy and practice in their

country; (2) barriers — what challenges or obstacles limit effective PPIE; and (3) resonance with the administrative perspective — the extent to which survey responses align with their organisation’s experience, including whether any elements were missing or perceived as over- or under-emphasised.

Qualitative inputs from patient organisations were analysed separately from expert survey finding using a thematic approach. The reflections from patient organisations are used to contextualise and interpret the expert survey findings, and to inform the discussion and recommendations presented in this report. To maintain anonymity, the reflections are presented in an aggregated manner without country specific focus. The names of contributing organisations without personal identifiers are listed in the results section.

Limitations

This analysis is subject to methodological limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings.

First, the use of expert surveys may introduce selection and information bias. Experts were nominated by Consortium members based on their expertise in cancer governance and public administration, which may have influenced the perspectives represented. The findings therefore reflect informed expert assessments rather than systematically verified institutional data. Furthermore, differences in respondents’ institutional positions, knowledge of national governance arrangements, and interpretation of survey questions may have affected the consistency of responses across countries.

Similarly, the perspectives provided by patient organisation representatives reflect informed stakeholder assessments grounded in their professional experience and engagement within national contexts. They should be understood as experiential and interpretative contributions that add contextual depth to the public administration survey findings.

Second, the response rate of the survey limits the generalisability of the findings. Of the 28 countries invited to participate, 16 provided responses. Non-response may be related to factors such as limited availability of experts, varying levels of institutional capacity, or differing national priorities regarding PPIE, which may influence the representativeness of the results.

Third, the composition of respondents varied across countries. While several responses were provided by representatives of ministries of health, others were submitted by affiliated organisations such as public health institutes, cancer centres, or research organisations. Although all respondents were selected based on their expertise in cancer governance, differences in institutional affiliation may affect comparability across countries.

Fourth, in two cases the data collection process deviated from the intended respondent structure. In Sweden, two survey submissions were received: one from a public administration representative and one from a patient organisation to whom the survey had been forwarded to. For the analysis of public administration responses, only the submission by the public administration representative was included, while the patient organisation submission was incorporated into the qualitative stakeholder perspective section of this report. In the Netherlands, the survey response was submitted by a representative of a patient organisation rather than a public administration actor, which should be considered when interpreting the findings for this country.

Finally, it is to be noted that because not all survey items were designated as mandatory, not all participating countries responded to every question. As a result, the number of valid responses differs across analyses presented in the Results section. Item-specific sample sizes are reported accordingly.

Results

Of the 30 ECHO S countries, 28 provided nominations of public administration experts and were subsequently invited to participate in the survey. These include Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, and Türkiye.

By the final deadline, 16 completed responses were received, corresponding to a response rate of 57%. Responses were submitted by public administration experts representing the institutions listed in Table 2. It is to be noted that many of the respondent institutions also gathered input from other experts in the field. The list below only shows the main respondents as listed in the Survey response.

Table 2. Participating organisation

Country	Main responding institution (National name)	Main responding institution (Translation)	Acronym
Austria	Bundesministerium für Arbeit, Soziales, Gesundheit, Pflege und Konsumentenschutz Gesundheit Österreich GmbH	Federal Ministry of Social Affairs, Health, Care and Consumer Protection National Public Health Institute	BMASGPK GÖG
Belgium	Sciensano	Public Health Institute	Sciensano
Croatia	Hrvatski zavod za javno zdravstvo	Institute of Public Health	HZJZ
Cyprus	Ινστιτούτο Έρευνας Καρκίνου Κύπρου	Cancer Research Institute University of Cyprus	CCRI UCY

Country	Main responding institution (National name)	Main responding institution (Translation)	Acronym
	Πανεπιστήμιο Κύπρου		
Finland	Kansallinen syöpäkeskus	Finnish Cancer Centre	FICAN
Germany	Gemeinsamer Bundesausschuss	Innovation Fund at the Federal Joint Committee	G-BA
Hungary	Egészségügyért Felelős Államtitkárság, Belügyminisztérium	Hungary State Secretariat for Health, Ministry of Interior	-
Ireland	Irish Health System – National Cancer Control Programme	-	HSE-NCCP
Italy	Fondazione Regionale per la Ricerca Biomedica	Regional Foundation for Biomedical Research	FRRB
The Netherlands	Nederlands Kanker Collectief	Dutch Cancer Collective	NKC
Norway	- retracted for anonymity -		
Portugal	Agência de Investigação Clínica e Inovação Biomédica	Agency for Clinical Research and Biomedical Innovation	AICIB
Romania	Asociația Centrul Pentru Inovație În Medicină	Centre for Innovation in Medicine	INOMED

Country	Main responding institution (National name)	Main responding institution (Translation)	Acronym
Slovakia	Národný onkologický ústav	National Oncology Institute of Slovakia	NOISK
Sweden	Socialstyrelsen	National Board of Health and Welfare	-
Turkey	T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı	General Directorate of Public Health (MoH)	-

Of the 16 countries that submitted survey responses, ECHO S Consortium partners nominated patient organisation representatives in 9 countries. Input was ultimately received from 5 patient organisations. The responding patient organisations are listed here:

- Belgian Patient Expert Centre
- The Alliance of Oncological Patient Organizations (Die Allianz der Onkologischen Patient: innenorganisationen)
- Dutch Federation of Cancer Patient Organisations (Nederlandse Federatie van Kankerpatiëntenorganisaties - NFK)
- Norwegian Cancer Society (Kreftforeningen)
- The Swedish Network against Cancer (Nätverket mot Cancer)

As noted in the previous section, the results are presented by thematic area, thereby contributing to a broader mapping of current governance practices and highlighting areas of progress, variation, and remaining gaps. For completeness, the full survey responses are provided in the annex.

Strengthen Public Sector Capacities (Area 1A)

The survey results reveal a heterogeneous landscape across European countries regarding the capacity of public administrations to support meaningful PPIE in oncology. While PPIE is widely perceived as an important or very important element of oncology policy, the extent to which this perceived importance is translated into institutionalised capacities, procedures, and resources varies substantially (Figure 1). Across the 16 countries surveyed, **8/16 countries** reported that **PPIE is perceived as “very important”, 2/16 as “extremely important”, 4/16 as “moderately important”, and 2/16 as “slightly important”**. No country reported that PPIE is “not important”.

Figure 1. Importance of patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development in public administration.

Institutional capacity-building and training

One key dimension of public sector capacity relates to the availability of publicly funded training opportunities for those involved in PPIE processes. As depicted in Figure 2, across the countries surveyed, structured training programmes or researchers, clinicians, and patient advocates are reported only in a limited number of cases and are unevenly distributed.

With regard to **training for researchers**, **7/16 countries** reported the existence of publicly funded training opportunities, while **7/16 countries** reported that no such training exists, and **2/16 countries** indicated that they could not answer. For **training programmes targeting clinicians**, only **6/16 countries** reported their existence, compared to **7/16 reporting no programmes** and **3/16 reporting uncertainty**. Training opportunities for **patient advocates** were reported slightly more frequently, with **7/16 countries** indicating that such programmes exist, while the remaining countries reported either no programmes or a lack of overview.

Figure 2. Confirmed funding for training programmes.

This pattern points to a broader challenge: even in countries where PPIE is valued, capacity-building is often not systematically addressed through dedicated training pathways. In numerical terms, **at least half of the surveyed countries report no publicly funded training opportunities for researchers or clinicians**, indicating that PPIE frequently relies on individual expertise, informal learning, or the capacities of patient organisations rather than being embedded in professional public administration structures.

Formalisation of roles, procedures, and decision-making

A second critical aspect of public sector capacity concerns the degree of formalisation of PPIE within oncology governance structures.

The survey further examined whether patients and the public are formally represented in national or regional oncology advisory structures, such as steering committees or ministry advisory groups. The majority of countries participating in this survey (**10/16**; 63%) reported **formal representation**, while 4 countries (25%) indicated no such formal structures (2 responses were unclear or missing). Among those with formal representation, involvement most frequently occurs through ministry advisory groups (10 countries) and national cancer steering committees (8 countries), with 11 countries also referencing *other* relevant advisory structures.

Country examples illustrate different governance approaches. Germany reported patient participation in a national cancer steering committee aimed at addressing problem areas in cancer care. Ireland provided details on representation within national cancer governance bodies linked to its Health Service Executive structures. These examples demonstrate that where formal representation exists, it is often embedded within established national governance mechanisms. Overall, the results indicate that while most countries have introduced formal advisory representation, this is not yet universal across all respondents.

Respondents were asked to indicate what type of rules exist for the participation of citizens, patients, and their representatives in oncology-related ministry advisory groups. The results indicate substantial variation in governance arrangements across countries. **3/16** countries (19%) reported that rules exist granting patients an advisory role, involving systematic consultation and documented input without voting rights. In each case **2/16** countries (13%) reported one of the following: no rules or practices for PPIE representation; *ad hoc* or informal inclusion without clear rules; rules provide consultative involvement only without structured influence; or that rules grant a co-decisive role with formal voting rights or shared decision-making.

These findings indicate a heterogeneous landscape in which ministry-level participation structures range from informal or absent arrangements to more institutionalised governance models. The relatively even distribution across response categories highlight that the formalisation of PPIE participation in ministry advisory groups is still evolving and differs substantially between countries.

These differences are further reflected in the existence of standard operating procedures (SOPs) or formal requirements for PPIE in programme evaluation. **7/16 countries** reported the existence of such SOPs, while **7/16 countries** reported that no SOPs exist, and **2/16 countries** could not answer. This indicates that **in more**

than half of the surveyed countries, PPIE is not formally embedded in evaluation processes, despite being recognised as important at the policy level.

This indicates that while structured participation mechanisms may exist in advisory bodies (as seen in earlier questions), formalised and legally embedded SOPs requiring PPIE across policy stages — including programme evaluation — are not yet consistently institutionalised across countries.

Stages of involvement across the oncology policy cycle

Respondents were asked at which stages PPIE usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities, including policy development, programme or service design, implementation, and monitoring and evaluation. The results (presented visually in Figure 3) show that involvement is most strongly embedded at the **policy development stage**, reported by 14/16 countries (88%). This is followed by involvement in **programme or service design** (10/16; 63%) and **implementation of policies or programmes** (9/16; 56%). Participation in **monitoring and evaluation** was reported by 7 countries (44%), indicating comparatively weaker engagement at later stages of the policy cycle.

Figure 3. Stages of PPIE across the oncology policy cycle (% of countries)

Qualitative comments highlight that in some countries, involvement extends into research-related consultation processes or protocol reviews. For example, Belgium referred to patient participation in the review of protocols, while Germany highlighted consultation processes linked to research and innovation activities. Overall, the findings indicate that PPIE is most consistently embedded in agenda-setting and strategic planning phases, with more limited but still notable participation in implementation and evaluation.

- **Policy development**

PPIE is most commonly reported at the policy development stage, with **14/16 countries** indicating involvement at this level. Countries such as Norway, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Sweden, the Netherlands, and Croatia reported that patients or the public are involved in the development of national strategies, laws, or regulatory frameworks related to oncology. Only two countries, Germany and Turkey, reported that PPIE does not typically take place at this stage, highlighting that policy development remains the primary entry point for participation across Europe.

- **Programme and service design**

Involvement at the level of programme or service design was reported by **10/16** countries. Examples include Ireland, Sweden, the Netherlands, Italy, and Croatia, where patient or public input extends beyond strategy development into the design of services or programmes. In contrast, six countries reported no involvement at this stage, indicating that participation often remains concentrated at higher, more strategic levels rather than extending into operational design.

- **Implementation**

At the implementation stage, involvement drops further. Only **9/16** countries reported involving patients or the public during implementation. Countries such as Ireland, Sweden, the Netherlands, and Italy reported engagement during roll-out or execution phases, while others reported no involvement once policies move into practice.

- **Monitoring and evaluation**

A similar pattern emerges for monitoring and evaluation, where **7/16** countries reported involvement. Countries such as Ireland, Sweden, the Netherlands, and Germany reported that patients or the public are involved

in reviewing outcomes or assessing progress, while the remaining countries reported no such involvement.

Patient and Public Involvement in National Cancer Control Plans (Area 1B)

The survey findings indicate that NCCPs or equivalent cancer strategies constitute a central policy instrument, as **all participating countries (16/16)** reported having such a plan or strategy in place. The most recent plans are from 2025 (Norway, Finland, Slovakia, Austria), while the oldest is from 1993 (Hungary), with most plans having been drafted or updated after 2017.

Co-creation and participation in NCCP development

Among the countries with an NCCP, **13/16** countries reported that patients or citizens were involved in the development of the plan, while **2/16** countries reported no such involvement. Patient organisations were the most frequently reported form of representation, followed by patient advocates and civil society organisations. More specialised roles, such as patient experts or community advocates, were reported in a smaller number of countries, indicating differing levels of participatory maturity.

These figures show that patient and public involvement in NCCP development is now common practice, but not universal, and that the depth and diversity of representation vary considerably between countries.

Involvement in the implementation phase of NCCP

The survey asked respondents to indicate the extent to which patients and/or citizens are involved in implementing the NCCP in their country, for example through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces. Across the responding countries, patient and citizen involvement was reported at varying levels of formalisation. Overall, **7/16** (44%) reported regular involvement with structured representation, such as mandated patient representatives, while **6/16** (38%) indicated that involvement occurs only occasionally, and **3/16 countries** (19%) reported regular but informal involvement without structured rules; Sweden reported both informal and structured forms of participation. Finland and Austria both indicated that, as their NCCPs were only recently established (in 2025 and

2026 respectively), implementation is still at an early stage and structured patient involvement, although planned as implementation progresses, is not yet in place.

Some responses also highlighted evolving or context-specific engagement practices. For example, Slovakia reported that patient representatives participated as an advisory body in drafting the updated Action Plans for 2026–2030. Sweden described the establishment of a NCMH, to be launched in 2026 under the name SweCan, which will include a general assembly of approximately 65 partners, around 15 of which are patient associations and civil society organisations, each holding equal voting rights. Overall, the findings indicate that while most countries report some degree of patient and citizen involvement in NCCP implementation, the level of institutionalisation and formal governance structures varies considerably across national contexts.

As shown in Figure 4, across the 15 countries that provided valid responses to this question (excluding one N/A response), Patient Organisation Representatives were the most frequently involved type (13/15; 87%), followed by Patient Advocates (6/15; 40%), while Patient Experts, Civil Society Organisation Representatives, and Public/Policy Experts were each reported in **4/15 countries (27%)**, and Community Advocates in **1/15 countries (7%)**.

Figure 4. Type of patient and/or citizen representatives involved in implementing the NCCP (% of countries)

In sum, Patient Organisation Representatives are by far the most commonly involved type (14/15 countries reporting involvement), signifying that structured or semi-structured participation is primarily channelled through formal patient organisations rather than individual advocates or broader community actors. Other forms of representation (**patient experts, civil society representatives, public/policy experts**) appear in a smaller but still notable group of countries, while **community advocates are rarely involved**.

Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion (Area 2)

This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.

The participating countries show that, in terms of accessibility, particular emphasis is placed on remote/hybrid events, barrier-free access to event venues and plain

language. Less commonly childcare is offered (**Error! Reference source not found.**). On average, **1.9 measures** are reported per country.

Figure 5. Accessibility measures used in PPIE activities within public administration frameworks (% of countries)

Of the participating countries, 4 reported other forms of support:

- Norway indicated that a structured partnership has been established as part of the Norwegian Cancer Strategy 2025–2035, encompassing coordinated efforts across all types of cancer.
- Germany reported that the Federal Joint Committee (G-BA) has a dedicated patient involvement specialist team responsible for organisational and content-related support, as outlined in [Social Code Book \[SGB\] V, Section 140f](#). This includes methodological and legal guidance, assistance with consultation documents, organising meetings, and supporting nomination procedures for patient representatives in the HTA processes of the G-BA and the Innovation Fund. Training is further provided by the G-BA's Medical Consultancy Department.

- The Netherlands highlighted that although other measures such as hybrid or remote participation, childcare, digital inclusion support and stipends are used in practice, they are not governed by systematic or legally mandated standard operating procedures for PPIE in oncology or in broader public administration involvement and therefore cannot be classified as systematically applied.

The extent to which structured partnerships or outreach activities exist with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups is answered inconsistently. **Approximately half** of the participating countries have such partnerships (**8/16**; 50%), while the other half do not (**4/16**; 25%) or are unable to answer this question (4/16; 25%).

In Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy partnerships or outreach activities are in place.

- Croatia reported examples of such groups like the Rare Tumour Patient Associations, Parent Associations of Pediatric Oncology Patients, Survivors of Malignant Diseases, etc.
- In Hungary, health visitor nurses in health care serve in underserved areas organized by the National Directorate General for Hospitals (OKFŐ).
- Ireland referred to the [NCCP Best Practice Guidance for Community Support Centres](#).
- Italy refers to oncology clinics and cancer networks such as “[Rete Oncologica](#)” in the Lombardy region.
- Slovakia indicated a position called the [Government Plenipotentiary for National Minorities](#), whose role is to represent and coordinate the interests of national minorities, including health issues.
- Sweden highlighted initiatives to reach groups in lower social / income and education levels, and the National Board of Health and Welfare participate in "Järvaveckan". Järvaveckan is a major annual civic and political event in Stockholm, designed to bring together citizens, politicians, businesses, authorities, and civil society to discuss democracy, inclusion, and social issues.

- The Netherlands referred to structured partnerships and outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and underrepresented groups. [Pharos](#), the national centre of expertise on health disparities, for example works structurally with policymakers, public institutions and professionals at national, regional and local levels to improve health equity for groups such as migrants, people with low literacy and low socioeconomic status. The Alliance for Health Literacy ([Alliantie Gezondheidsvaardigheden](#)) brings together public bodies, civil-society organisations and healthcare actors to support people with limited health literacy. Other examples are [National programmes on digital inclusion](#) involve structured collaboration between the Dutch government, municipalities, libraries and civil-society partners to reduce digital exclusion of vulnerable groups.
- Austria noted that collaborations and funding activities exist, such as the funding/support of some self-help organisations including oncology related groups.

Participation Influences Transparent Decisions (Area 3)

This area examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.

The representation of participants in activities organised by public administration is monitored (internally) in **4/16** and publicly reported in **9/16** participating countries. In **4/16** countries there is no reporting.

The results of the public consultation on cancer policy conducted by the participating organisations are made publicly available in most countries. Only **3/16** countries do not report results. The scope of the publication varies. A summary is published in **7/16** countries. In **4 countries**, the responses are also published. No country reported the publication with responses and audit/appeal.

All countries share consultation outcomes. On average, **2,7 different** forms are used (variance of 0 to 7). The results are most often published on the institution's official website (8/16) and presented at public events, workshops, or conferences (7/16). 3 countries reported other forms. In Finland outcomes are published on Ministry of Justice's online consultation platform. Figure 6 shows further details.

Figure 6. Forms in which consultation outcomes are shared among participating countries (% of countries)

Active Mechanisms in Policy/Legislation Development (Area 4)

This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology — from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation — and the level of involvement at each stage.

Figure 7 shows a very diverse picture in terms of both the phase of participation and the level of participation.

It is important to note that due to the missing response from one country (Turkey), the sample size (n) for the specific question item has been reduced accordingly.

Except for one country, all countries engage patients and the public in identifying problems. 5/15 countries do so on an ad hoc basis, whereas 9/15 rely on regular consultations or advisory participation.

12/15 countries participate in the design phase, with structured participation being the most common form (5 out of 16 countries).

Apart from one country, all responding countries involve patients and the public in the data collection phase, again most commonly in a structured form.

Participation in the data analysis phase takes place **in 12/15** countries, primarily on an *ad hoc* basis or in the form of regular consultation.

Participation in the dissemination of results takes place in **11/15 countries**, particularly in the form of regular consultation.

Participation in implementation takes place in **14/15** countries, with participation mostly informal or on an *ad hoc* basis. A similar picture emerges for the monitoring and evaluation phase where **12/15 countries** report patient and public involvement primarily on an *ad hoc* basis.

Figure 7. Heatmap on the extent of involvement of patients and the public in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (sorted by average scores, scores range from 1 to 5)

Adequate and Sustainable Resources (Area 5)

This section addressed the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.

Countries were asked whether sustainable public sector resources—such as budget, staff, or technical support—are allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology-related activities. Where relevant, respondents provided comments describing the purpose and volume of these resources. Figure 8 shows a

cross-country mapping of public sector resources dedicated to enabling effective PPIE within oncology activities.

Figure 8. Mapping of public sector resources allocated to support effective PPIE in oncology activities (countries sorted alphabetically)

A total of **7/16 countries** reported that no sustainable resources are available. Furthermore, **4 countries (Ireland, Italy, Sweden, Austria)** indicated that funds exist for support facilities such as competence centre participation.

- Austria indicated that these funds are not specifically allocated for oncology-related activities, but rather for supporting self-help organisations and patient participation.
- Sweden highlighted that national funds and regional agreements provide financing for the Regional Cancer Centre’s (RCC) national supportive roles and activities, including patient cooperation.

Funds for accompanying research were reported by **5 countries (Ireland, Croatia, Italy, Sweden, Austria)**, while **6 countries (Germany, Ireland, Croatia, Finland, Sweden, Austria)** stated that funds are available for patient organisations.

- Croatia reported that, health care institutions and researchers frequently collaborate with patient organisations on research projects. At the local, county, and city levels in Croatia, public budgets are allocated to support the work of associations (e.g., patient organisations), including the provision of business premises at symbolic or no cost. The specific amounts vary by local government unit and are coordinated annually, with all allocations publicly disclosed on the respective local government websites.
- Sweden noted that funding for research is provided through agreements covering competencies, knowledge, data collection, quality registers, and clinical trials. Furthermore, regional funding supports local patient organisations, while national funding is allocated to national patient organisations.
- Austria indicated that research funding includes support for organisations such as the LBG Open Innovation in Science Centre (LBG OIS) and for research initiatives delivered through programmes like the Cancer Mission Lab. Funding for patient organisations is not oncology specific. Instead, it is provided more broadly to self-help organisations across disease areas, with oncology groups included within this general support framework.
- Germany highlighted that, statutory health insurance funds are legally required to support health related self-help, providing ongoing institutional funding for self-help groups and patient organisations at federal, state, and regional levels. Funding is provided both through joint community funding across all health insurance funds and through lumpsum basic support, ensuring stable resources for patient organisations, including those active in oncology.

In addition, **3/16 countries (Germany, Ireland, Sweden)** reported the availability of funds for expense allowances or similar reimbursements. Other types of resources or funding mechanisms were mentioned by **3 countries (Germany, Finland, the Netherlands)**.

- Germany indicated that staff and technical support are provided through the Federal Joint Committee (Gemeinsamer Bundesausschuss, G-BA) and

the Innovation Fund, within which patient participation is legally mandated in research projects initiated by the German Federal Government, and all associated costs, including personnel and equipment, can be covered through this [funding framework](#).

- Finland reported that, although no dedicated funding streams exist, PPIE activities are carried out within organisations' general operating budgets.
- The Netherlands noted no sustainable or earmarked public-sector resources for PPIE in oncology, and while patient organisations may receive general funding, these funds are not specifically allocated to support PPIE in oncology policy or programme development.

Countries were asked whether a national or regional policy exists on the remuneration or reimbursement of patient or public contributors. This includes policies covering fees, reimbursement of travel costs, compensation for time, or similar forms of financial recognition for participation. A total of **5 out of 16 countries** reported that such a policy exists. **Over half (56.3%, n=9)** indicated that no such policy is currently in place, while **2 out of 16 countries** stated that they could not answer the question. To contextualize the findings, countries were asked to describe the regulations or guidelines related to the remuneration or reimbursement of patient or public contributors:

- Germany indicated that daily allowances, compensation for loss of earnings, and travel expenses can be claimed in contexts involving the Federal Ministry of Health, the Federal Ministry of Education and Research, the Federal Joint Committee (G-BA), and the Innovation Fund. Formal guidance covering [reimbursement of travel expenses](#) and the [calculation of loss of earnings](#) in the context of federal-level participation processes were referenced.
- Ireland referred to the [HSE National Policy on the Reimbursement of Expenses for Patient and Service User Partners](#), which outlines procedures for covering contributor expenses.
- Croatia indicated that [national instructions](#) exist for co-financing travel expenses and time compensation for members of working groups involved in developing health-related laws and regulations.

- Finland explained that patient representatives typically receive compensation for participating in advisory group meetings at hospitals.
- Sweden described remuneration arrangements for participation in patient counselling groups, while also highlighting ongoing discussions about limitations affecting individuals on permanent sick leave. Additionally, it was noted that, under RCC policy, patient and relative representatives are entitled to reimbursement of travel expenses and compensation for time dedicated to their assignments.

Civil Society Capacity Strengthening (Area 6)

This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.

Question 31 explores whether initiatives exist to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations to participate effectively in relevant processes.

Figure 9 shows a rather diverse picture of the available capacity-strengthening initiatives in the participating countries.

Figure 9. Extent of capacity building initiatives (training, technical support, funding schemes) for patient and civil society participation

For **training initiatives** (e.g., for public administration staff), **3 out of 16 countries** reported that such initiatives take place only on an ad hoc basis. Regular trainings without a formal policy basis were reported by **a quarter**, whereas **3 out of 16 countries** indicated that trainings are regularly provided and supported by policy or legislation. **Over a third (37.5%, n=6)** of countries reported that no such training initiatives exist or that the question was not applicable. To complement this quantitative overview, countries were asked to provide further information illustrating training initiatives.

- Belgium reported that training opportunities are offered on an *ad hoc* basis through the [Patient Expert Centre](#).

- Germany indicated that various training and qualification activities are provided by [self-help organisations](#), including [participatory research training](#) and programmes offered by [BAG Selbsthilfe](#).
- Ireland noted that structured training is available through national programmes, including community cancer support centres and survivorship initiatives.
- Croatia outlined that patient and civil society organisations receive support through national mechanisms, and that the National Agency for Mobility and EU Programmes ([AMPEU](#)) facilitates training and participation in EU funded projects.
- Italy reported that [APEnet](#), a network of universities and research bodies for public engagement, supports public engagement by providing shared resources and opportunities for knowledge exchange.
- Finland stated that training is provided on an ad hoc basis, including the European Patients' Academy on Therapeutic Innovation (EUPATI) Finland and sessions for patient advisory group members organised by hospitals.
- Austria noted that the Austrian Competence and Support Center for SelfHelp (ÖKUSS), funded by the Ministry of Health and national health insurance, provides structured training for self-help organisations.

For **technical support**, **2/16 countries** reported ad hoc initiatives. Regular initiatives without formal policy support were selected by **3/16 countries**, and **2/16 countries** indicated that technical support is provided regularly and backed by policy or legislation. Additionally, **over half of the countries (9/16; 56%)** stated that no technical support initiatives exist. To complement this quantitative overview, countries were asked to provide further information illustrating technical support initiatives.

For **funding schemes**, **2/16 countries** reported ad hoc funding opportunities. Regular funding opportunities without a policy basis were indicated by **2/16 countries**, while **a quarter (4/16; 25%)** reported regular funding schemes supported by policy or legislation. **Half of the countries (8/16; 50%)** indicated that no such funding schemes are available.

- Croatia explained that funding is supported at the national level, with mechanisms enabling patient associations and civil society to participate in project activities, including access to EU-funded programmes via [AMPEU](#).
- Austria has reported that ÖKUSS (Österreichische Kompetenz- und Servicestelle für Selbsthilfe) administers funding for self-help organisations. This funding is provided by the national social health insurance system (Sozialversicherung).

For **other capacity-strengthening initiatives**, ad hoc measures were reported by **1/16 countries**. Regular initiatives without a formal policy basis were mentioned by **1/16 countries**, and **2/16 countries** indicated regular initiatives supported by policy or legislation. A total of **12/16 countries** reported that no other initiatives exist. To contextualise these results, the following country specific explanations were provided in response to the other capacity-strengthening initiatives:

- Sweden reported that education and training are provided internally by patient organisations to prepare representatives for their roles. Additional specialised training in funding and resource management is available through external providers such as GIVA Sweden, which supports capacity-building in civil society organisations.
- Austria noted that a participation strategy for the health care system is currently being developed and financed by the MoH.
- Cyprus highlighted, that initiatives which aim to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations effective participation are being developed.
- Portugal indicated that, while there are no capacity-strengthening initiatives, attempts are being made to engage and listen to needs, to work on a strategy for better patient involvement and empowerment.

Monitoring and Evaluation (Area 7)

Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.

Countries were asked whether their organisations track and report outcome indicators linking PPIE activities to decision-making processes. Figure 10 illustrates a rather diverse picture in terms of tracking and reporting of outcome indicators.

Figure 10. Country practices in tracking PPIE inked outcome indicators (countries sorted alphabetically).

None of the countries confirmed systematic tracking and reporting of outcome indicators. Tracking without systematic reporting occurs in **2 countries (Ireland, Sweden)**, while Ireland also tracks or reports outcome indicators only occasionally or on an *ad hoc* basis. In **4 countries (Belgium, Romania, Finland, Slovakia)**, the development of such indicators is planned. Meanwhile **6 countries (Norway, Germany, Croatia, Italy, Cyprus, Portugal)** reported that no such indicators are currently tracked or reported. Additionally, **1 country (Turkey)** selected “Don’t know / Not applicable,” and **4 countries (Slovakia, Sweden, the Netherlands, Austria)**

chose “Other.” The following country-specific explanations were provided in response to the “Other” category:

- Slovakia reported that the Patient Council at the NCI reports its activities publicly on the NCI website.
- The Netherlands noted that the NKC nor any affiliated entities systematically track or report outcome indicators linking PPIE to decision-making (e.g., policy changes, resource allocation, access or equity impacts). While patient input informs agenda-setting and programme development, there is no published national framework that measures downstream effects of PPIE in oncology, apart from reporting on the implementation of the Netherlands.
- Austria outlined that the project and performance catalogue of GÖG lists committees and their members. A one-time [2023 survey by GÖG](#) provides an overview of existing participation processes. It remains under consideration whether patient involvement will be integrated into the development of patient pathways.

To contextualise these findings, countries that track and/or report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes, where asked to provide additional information on the type of indicator used and how they are monitored or reported.

- Slovakia reported that outcome indicators are planned to be included in the updated Action Plans (2026–2030) of the National Oncology Programme, where they will be used for evaluation purposes.
- Sweden explained that outcomes are systematically tracked, although structured changes do not always follow from the results. Monitoring includes lead times, quality parameters in care processes, patient-reported experience measures (PREMs), patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs), and compliance with treatment guidelines. While this provides a comprehensive evaluation framework, translating insights into practice remains a challenge.

Integrated Heatmap

A heatmap (Figure 11) was developed to visualise the level of implementation of PPIE across multiple dimensions of oncology policy and programme development in the surveyed countries.

Survey responses were recoded into a unified ordinal scale ranging from 0 to 2 to allow comparability across items with different response formats. The scale reflected the degree of institutionalisation and formalisation of involvement:

2 = implemented

1.5 = mostly implemented

1 = partially implemented

0.5 = minimally implemented

0 = inexistent

N/A = missing or not classifiable

For items with categorical response options, values were assigned based on the extent to which mechanisms were formalised, structured, and embedded in policy processes. Where necessary, inverse-coded items were recoded so that higher values consistently reflected higher levels of implementation.

Countries were ordered based on their overall level of implementation, calculated as the mean score across all available items, to facilitate comparison across settings.

The scoring framework represents an analytic transformation of survey responses and should be interpreted as an indicative measure of implementation rather than a validated index.

Figure 11. Heatmap on implementation levels of PPIE in cancer policy and governance

Results from Patient Organisation Perspectives

Importantly, the reflections provided by patient organisations contribute to a broader understanding of structural enablers and constraints influencing effective and sustainable PPIE development. They also informed the formulation of the key recommendations presented at the end of this report, ensuring that these reflect not only institutional self-assessments but also external stakeholder perspectives.

It should be noted that the structure, mandate, and degree of formal recognition of patient organisations vary considerably across countries. Consequently, the insights gathered are qualitative and exploratory in nature and do not aim to provide a fully representative national assessment, but rather to reflect informed stakeholder perspectives within each respective context.

Reflections on public administration responses

Patient organisations responses generally recognise parts of the administrative accounts, especially where formal structures for involvement are described. In systems with legally anchored user involvement and defined committees within hospitals and health authorities, the administrative depiction largely aligns with patient organisations' experience that there are avenues to participate and be heard. One organisation emphasised that these structures exist alongside training and joint learning offers, and that this is broadly reflected in the survey responses.

At the same time, patient organisations highlighted several discrepancies in the experiences of PPIE in oncology policy and practice. In one context, it is explicitly stated that PPIE is not a significant driver of policymaking and that patients are not systematically involved. Consultation formats are not adapted when patients cannot attend, which undermines the claim of inclusive practice. Another respondent agrees that while structures are acknowledged in the public administrative responses, the role of patient organisations in recruiting, preparing, and supporting representatives is under described, as is their contribution across levels (from national strategy processes to clinical and research settings).

Furthermore, patient representatives highlight a significant gap between administrative accounts of available funding and the actual experience of patient organisations. Despite claims of support (e.g., financial resources), the lack of meaningful, accessible, and sustainable financial and organisational resources,

such as compensation for representatives, capacity building mechanisms, and stable funding streams, continues to limit their ability to represent patients effectively and consistently.

Respondents also stress the need to distinguish between structural inclusion (“a seat at the table”) and quality of influence (cocreation and follow through), noting that this distinction is not always explicit in the responses given by public representatives. In yet another setting, despite legal provision for client councils, patient organisations report that true equality remains difficult to achieve, and involvement is still too often treated as a box ticking exercise.

Overall administrative accounts align with the experience of patient representatives in recognizing the presence of participatory elements. However, patient organisations report that administrative narratives tend to overestimate the degree of institutionalisation and the structural impact of patient involvement, while underestimating persistent gaps in transparency, accountability, mandatory frameworks, and equity.

Taken together, these reflections highlight **a common theme: administrative narratives often capture formal arrangements but fail to reflect the variability in real-world practice, the preparedness and support needs of patient organisations, and the gap between the mere presence of patient involvement and its actual influence.** In line with this, one patient organisation response indicated that, although participatory elements are recognised, the survey may present patient involvement as more institutionalised and structurally influential than it is in practice, while giving too little attention to persistent gaps in transparency, accountability, mandatory frameworks, and the inclusion of underrepresented or vulnerable groups.

Facilitators and barriers to meaningful PPIE according to Patient Organisation responses

Across the patient organisations consulted, experiences with PPIE in oncology policy and practice vary considerably, but several overarching themes emerge regarding what enables, and what limits, meaningful participation.

Identified facilitators

In some health systems, meaningful PPIE is supported by clear legal and institutional structures that embed patient participation into governance processes. These include formally established user committees, defined roles within hospital and system level structures, and procedures for appointing representatives in a transparent manner. Countries with these mechanisms in place, such as those where user involvement is a statutory requirement, tend to report that patient representatives are more often heard and able to influence decisions.

One patient organisation response stated that, in practice, patient organisations themselves often constitute the strongest facilitating force for driving meaningful patient engagement forward via their strong advocacy work. In particular, outcomes have been strengthened in areas like, guideline development, patient pathways, clinical research, psychosocial care, and evaluation processes - where early and structured engagement yields more relevant and sustainable outcomes. In some contexts, industry associations routinely include patient organisations in their events and discussions, and there is a growing trend of companies integrating patient engagement pathways that emphasise early involvement.

It was also mentioned that an increasingly important **external catalyst for meaningful PPIE is the influence of European frameworks and cross-border collaborations.** Initiatives such as **Europe's Beating Cancer Plan**, the **EU Mission on Cancer**, and **broader EU-level patient engagement standards** have created political expectations and reference points that indirectly influence national discussions. Participation in European projects and networks exposes national actors to more advanced models of institutionalised PPIE, which highlights both opportunities and existing gaps within the national systems and contributes to embedding more professional standards and terminology in national debates. Additionally, cross-border collaboration and connections between patient experts further strengthens awareness of meaningful PPIE. It is however important to note, that this relies according to the responses, heavily on the dedication and efforts of the individual patient experts and is not anchored in institutional design.

Additionally, **financial and organisational support** is seen as another important enabler, **including compensation for representatives and funding streams that allow patient organisations to build capacity.** Where such funding exists, it helps professionalise participation, ensure continuity, and diversify who can take on

representative roles. Training and competence building further strengthen patient involvement; in some settings, hospital-based training programmes, e-learning modules, and even university-level courses prepare patient representatives for system level or research related engagement. These forms of structured preparation are also valued for enabling a more equal dialogue between patients, clinicians, researchers and policymakers.

Patient organisations also highlight the **benefits of cultural shifts within health systems**, where political messaging and institutional expectations increasingly reinforce the idea that **patients should be central to care and system development**. Over time, this has helped to normalise patient participation and support more constructive interactions. In oncology, quality improvement frameworks, including those linked to CCC accreditation, have further strengthened structured patient involvement by making it an integral part of governance and continuous quality development. However, it was also noted that this cultural shift is not uniform across settings and countries. While some countries report its positive impact on PPIE others highlight that a broader cultural shift and paradigm change towards recognising patients as equal partners in governance has not yet taken place.

Overall, the current facilitating factors are still largely based on individual initiatives, European impulses, and selective institutional openness. They provide a starting point, but they do not yet constitute a fully institutionalised or binding participation culture.

Identified barriers

Despite these advances, patient organisations also identified a set of persistent obstacles that limit comprehensive and effective PPIE.

One major challenge is the **lack of formal recognition and sustainable funding** for patient organisations in some systems. Without stable financial support or official status, organisations struggle to build the capacity needed to represent patients effectively and consistently. Where remuneration models for patient representation are absent and **voluntary engagement is expected at the same strategic level as salaried professionals, unequal power dynamics become visible**. This is particularly evident in contexts where many cancer types have no dedicated patient organisation at all, limiting both representation and the diversity of voices feeding into oncology policy.

Even where structures exist, patient organisations describe significant **practical barriers to participation**. Meetings may be scheduled at times that are inaccessible to working patients or caregivers, and costs of participation are not always reimbursed. **Technical language and complex governance processes** can further hinder effective engagement unless support and facilitation are provided. As a result, even invited representatives can find it challenging to contribute meaningfully, **and low attendance may be interpreted as a lack of interest rather than a reflection of structural barriers**.

Another recurring barrier relates to the **workload and expectations placed on patient representatives**. System level roles can be demanding, time intensive, and difficult to combine with employment, illness, or caregiving responsibilities.

These pressures are intensified in the **absence of clearly defined roles and competencies**, specifically in settings where there is no shared national understanding of what distinguishes a Patient Advocate, a Patient Expert or a self-help representative. This can lead to unclear expectations and situations in which representatives are expected to cover all dimensions at once. However, in systems undergoing institutional stress, healthcare professionals may lack the time or capacity to engage in genuine cocreation, **reducing patient involvement to information sharing rather than joint decision making**. These pressures can also **limit diversity**, as only individuals with substantial availability or specific professional backgrounds may be able to participate.

Diversity in PPIE becomes further restricted in settings where comprehensive diversity and inclusion strategy in the context of PPIE are absent. When the involvement of vulnerable or underrepresented groups is not systematically ensured, engagement tends to focus on well-organised indications with established advocacy structures. This may create **inequities in representation and leaves certain patient populations without a voice in governance processes**.

Patient organisations also highlight **systemic barriers** in countries where **healthcare governance is a shared responsibility between federal and regional levels**, blending centralized legislation with decentralized implementation. The distribution of responsibilities across multiple regional authorities results in **fragmented participation practices**, with no harmonised national standards to ensure consistent involvement across regions. This lack of coherence creates uneven opportunities for engagement and makes it difficult to establish participation as a stable, institutionalised component of decision-making. As a

result, patient organisations often face additional administrative burden, limiting their ability to contribute effectively and sustainably across the system.

Patient organisations additionally stress a gap between **formal inclusion and substantive influence**. While many systems refer to PPIE as a policy priority, patient representatives frequently stated that their contributions do not significantly shape decisions. National cancer strategies are sometimes described as **inclusive on paper, while integrating patient perspectives only marginally in practice**. The perception that involvement is sometimes treated as a **procedural requirement rather than as valued expertise** is particularly prominent in settings where legal structures exist, but **cultural or organisational attitudes have not fully aligned with the intention of co-creation**.

Furthermore, patient organisations report that meaningful patient involvement remains dependent on discretionary openness rather than being embedded as a standard principle of governance. This is further reflected in the **lack of systematic outcome measurements** in several settings. Where feedback loops and transparency are largely absent, it remains unclear whether meaningful change, as a result of patient input, has taken place.

Patient organisations also emphasise the **lack of structured, accessible, and adequately funded training opportunities** as a major barrier to meaningful participation. While in some settings there have been efforts to establish more formalised pathways, such as academic training programmes for patient representatives aiming to develop into patient experts, these initiatives largely have not yet materialised. A patient representative reported that attempts to introduce such programmes faced substantial resistance from key stakeholders, and therefore never progressed to implementation. This illustrates a broader challenge: the system has not yet created an enabling environment where the professional development of patient representatives is seen as a shared and strategic responsibility.

Similarly, it was noted that initiatives aimed at providing **training on patient involvement to healthcare professionals** have struggled to gain traction, with **limited interest from staff in relevant institutions**. From a patient perspective, this highlights a **cultural gap**: meaningful involvement requires not only empowered patient representatives but also **professionals who understand and value participatory approaches**. Without parallel capacity-building on both sides, opportunities for engagement remain constrained.

In settings where training opportunities for patient representatives exist, they tend to be limited in scope and depth, often providing only basic or introductory knowledge. In addition, the lack of stable, basic funding for patient organisations means that **capacity-building** depends heavily on the ability to secure external fundraising, which is not feasible for many groups. As a result, training efforts remain fragmented and insufficient to produce a critical mass of qualified patient experts who can participate at scale.

One of the respondent patient organisations concludes that this situation creates a **structural bottleneck**: even when policymakers or institutions express openness to strengthening patient involvement and seek to engage more systematically, the number of adequately trained and resourced patient representatives is often too small to meet the demand. Many systems have not invested enough in preparing the patient community for broader, more strategic participation. Consequently, patient involvement risks depending on a very small group of highly committed individuals, rather than being embedded within a resilient, diverse ecosystem of trained advocates.

In this sense, while the growing recognition of the importance of patient participation is an important step forward and patient organisations recognise the progress that has been made, the necessary enabling conditions are still not sufficiently in place to support meaningful and sustainable involvement.

Learnings & Discussion

The following overview provides insights from both the responses given by public administration experts working in the field of health and cancer policy in **16 European countries**, as well as qualitative reflections from **5 patient organisation representatives**. This section summarises responses, showcasing current approaches to PPIE in oncology policy and programme development.

Overall, the findings indicate that PPIE is widely recognised as an important element of oncology governance across participating countries. **However, the degree to which this recognition is translated into institutionalised structures, resources, and procedures varies considerably across systems.** Across countries, formal participation mechanisms are present in more than half of the surveyed systems, although co-decisive forms of participation remain limited. Participation most frequently occurs during policy development, while involvement tends to decrease at later stages of the policy and programme cycle, particularly during implementation and evaluation. Measures supporting accessibility and inclusion are reported in several countries but are not consistently applied. Similarly, dedicated resources, structured capacity-building initiatives, and monitoring systems linking PPIE to decision-making outcomes are unevenly developed.

Against this background, the following observations and recommendations were developed by the authors based on the survey findings and the responses from patient organisations. To ensure consistency with the established indicators and their connection to the WHO resolution areas, the recommendations are structured in line with the seven areas of the WHO framework on social participation, adapted to the context of cancer policy and governance.

Strengthen Public Sector Capacities (Area 1A and 1B)

Strengthen Public Sector Capacities (Area 1A)

Although PPIE is widely recognised as an important element of oncology governance, this recognition is not yet consistently translated into routine administrative practice. In many countries, participation still seems to depend more on individual commitment, informal arrangements, or existing organisational cultures than on stable institutional structures and clearly defined procedures. The uneven provision of training and the limited presence of formal operating

procedures indicate that PPIE is often not yet fully embedded as a standard component of governance. The fact that involvement is stronger in agenda setting and policy design than in implementation, monitoring, and evaluation also points to a more consultative than fully integrated model of participation. Overall, the results highlight an implementation gap, with the key challenge being not whether PPIE is considered valuable, but how it can be institutionalised more consistently and sustainably across the full oncology policy cycle.

National Cancer Control Plans (Area 1B)

NCCPs represent an important entry point for participation. While most countries involve patients or citizens in developing these plans, participation often remains limited in depth and is primarily channelled through patient organisations rather than broader or more diverse forms of representation. This suggests that PPIE is present within national cancer planning but not always embedded through stable governance arrangements across implementation and evaluation. More broadly, the overall picture remains one of uneven institutionalisation, where formal structures may exist, but the practical conditions needed for effective participation are not yet consistently in place. The perspective of patient organisations reinforces this by showing that meaningful engagement depends not only on rules or committees, but also on whether administrations genuinely value experiential knowledge and create conditions in which participation can influence decisions rather than merely ensure representation.

To address these points public administrations may consider:

- Strengthening institutional culture and staff capabilities to support engagement that goes beyond procedural fulfilment and enables meaningful influence.
- Developing comprehensive institutional frameworks for PPIE that move beyond recognition of its importance toward clearly defined roles, responsibilities, and procedures across all stages of the oncology policy cycle.
- Establishing publicly funded and systematic training programmes for public administration staff, healthcare professionals, and patient representatives to strengthen professional competencies for participation and engagement processes.

- Supporting the development of structured implementation frameworks for patient involvement in National Cancer Control Plans, ensuring continuity between policy design and implementation.

Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion (Area 2)

Approaches to accessibility and inclusion in oncology related PPIE vary considerably across countries and appear to be shaped more by national or organisational practice than by shared standards. While many systems have adopted relatively low threshold measures such as hybrid participation formats, accessible venues, and easy to understand communication, more resource intensive forms of support are less consistently available. This indicates that inclusion is often understood primarily in logistical terms, whereas the broader structural conditions that enable sustained and equitable participation receive less systematic attention. The uneven and often informal collaboration with underserved or underrepresented groups further indicates that diversity in participation is not yet embedded as a routine governance objective. Patient organisations underline this gap by drawing attention to the practical demands participation places on individuals, showing that accessibility is not only about being invited, but also about whether people realistically have the time, flexibility, support, and capacity to take part.

To improve accessibility, diversity and inclusion, public administrations may consider:

- Formalise and standardise accessibility measures such as hybrid participation, childcare, digital inclusion support and plain language communication through national guidelines or SOPs.
- Develop structured partnerships with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups to ensure sustained outreach and culturally appropriate engagement.
- Provide systematic reimbursement and compensation for time, travel and participation costs to reduce financial barriers and enable equitable involvement.

- Invest in capacity building and support structures, such as dedicated teams, training programmes and legal/methodological guidance for patient representatives.
- Strengthen digital inclusion initiatives, ensuring that remote participation does not exclude groups with low digital literacy or limited access to technology.
- Ensure that participation processes minimise avoidable burden and are designed to accommodate the time constraints and health/social realities of patient representatives, helping prevent exclusion driven by workload or competing responsibilities.
- Develop national diversity and inclusion strategies to ensure involvement of underrepresented and vulnerable groups in oncology governance.

Participation Influences Transparent Decisions (Area 3)

The transparency of public participation in cancer policy varies significantly from country to country. Only a few countries use systematic approaches to monitor or publicly report on consultation process participation, and the way this information is shared varies considerably. While most countries publish consultation outcomes, the level of detail varies substantially, ranging from brief, high-level summaries to more comprehensive documentation. Where monitoring of participation is absent or limited, it becomes difficult to judge which perspectives are included and which may be missing. The fact that no country reported mechanisms for auditing or formally challenging published consultation results further demonstrates that transparency often focuses on communicating outcomes rather than enabling closer scrutiny of how participation has shaped decision-making. Although consultation outcomes are typically disseminated through multiple channels – such as official websites or public events – standards for reporting, accessibility, and accountability remain inconsistent. Some countries enhance visibility through centralised digital platforms, yet overall, practices lack uniformity, limiting comparability and transparency across systems.

To improve transparent decisions, public administrations may consider:

- Establish minimum reporting standards for documenting and publishing participation processes and results.

- Expand accessible dissemination channels, such as centralised online platforms or community outreach.
- Build institutional capacity to ensure transparent, consistent reporting across all oncology related consultations.

Active Mechanisms in Policy/Legislation Development (Area 4)

PPIE is broadly embedded across the oncology policy cycle in the examined countries, yet it generally occurs through informal or *ad hoc* practices rather than through systematic, continuous structures. Patient and Public are commonly engaged in early stages such as problem identification and policy design, often through routine consultation or structured participation formats. Formalised methods are also frequently used during data collection. However, engagement tends to become less organised in later phases, including data analysis, dissemination, implementation, and monitoring and evaluation, where input is typically gathered through non-systematic mechanisms. Overall, while participation is widespread, consistent and institutionalised approaches to involving patients and the public remain limited, pointing to the need to strengthen continuity across the full policy cycle.

To improve active mechanism in policy/legislation development, public administrations may consider:

- Develop clear national guidelines defining roles, responsibilities and participation formats for patients and the public throughout oncology policy cycles.
- Strengthen involvement in later stages—implementation, monitoring and evaluation—to ensure patient perspectives meaningfully influence outcomes.
- Invest in capacity building for both public institutions and patient groups to support informed, high-quality participation.

Adequate and Sustainable Resources (Area 5)

The uneven provision of sustainable public sector resources specifically earmarked for participation activities highlights differences in how firmly PPIE is anchored within national oncology governance in practice. Where participation is not supported by clear and predictable funding, it is more likely to rely on temporary arrangements, broader institutional budgets, or the existing capacities of patient organisations. This can influence not only the continuity of engagement, but also the extent to which participation can be organised in a consistent and inclusive way. In this regard, resourcing is not only a practical matter, but also an indication of how far participation is embedded as a regular part of governance.

The perspective of patient organisations reinforces this point by showing that meaningful engagement requires long term institutional support, formal recognition, and compensation arrangements that reduce the practical burden of participation. Without these conditions, participation may remain formally possible, but in practice accessible mainly to those with sufficient time, financial flexibility, or organisational backing.

To improve sustainability and effectiveness, public administrations may consider:

- Establishing dedicated and predictable funding streams for PPIE activities in oncology.
- Clarifying the purpose and scope of available resources, including staffing, technical support, and operational budgets.
- Embedding PPIE as a compulsory element of all research and programme proposals submitted for grant funding.
- Integrating PPIE-related costs into research and programme funding frameworks, including coordination, facilitation, and administrative support.
- Ensuring that funding mechanisms support both national and local levels of engagement.
- Formally recognising patient organisations as strategic partners through stable institutional funding.

Overall, clearer alignment between participation expectations and available resources may contribute to the sustainability and continuity of PPIE activities.

Civil Society Capacity Strengthening (Area 6)

Capacity-strengthening initiatives for patient organisations and civil society appears to be present in a number of countries but are often not yet organised on a stable and continuous basis. Where support takes the form of *ad hoc* or project-based initiatives, opportunities for learning and development may remain uneven over time and across organisations. This matters because the ability to participate effectively is closely linked to whether patient organisations have access to training, funding, and practical support that allow them to engage on more equal terms with institutional actors. The perspective of patient organisations underlines that competence building can improve both confidence and the quality of dialogue in participatory processes. At the same time, the comparatively limited development of technical support points to an area where further strengthening could help participation become more consistent and accessible, particularly for smaller organisations and groups that are less well resourced. Where capacity building is carried mainly by patient organisations themselves, this can strengthen ownership, but complementary public sector support remains important for wider reach and longer-term continuity.

To strengthen capacity in a systematic way, public administrations may consider:

- Establishing regular training programmes for both patient representatives and public administration staff.
- Providing technical support structures, such as competence centres or advisory services, that assist organisations in participating effectively.
- Supporting knowledge exchange platforms that allow patient organisations, researchers, and policymakers to share experiences and good practices.
- Linking funding schemes to capacity-building objectives to ensure that organisations can sustainably engage in participation processes.

Monitoring and Evaluation (Area 7)

Systematic monitoring and reporting of outcome indicators linking PPIE activities to decision-making processes remain largely absent across surveyed countries. In the absence of comprehensive frameworks for assessing the impact of participation, it remains difficult to determine whether and how participation influences policy or programme outcomes.

Examples identified in the survey, such as Sweden's integration of patient-reported outcome and experience measures into broader quality monitoring systems and Slovakia's plans to introduce participation related indicators within future NCCPs, illustrate possible ways of embedding participation into existing evaluation structures rather than establishing separate reporting systems. At the same time, the findings show that monitoring and reporting alone do not necessarily lead to structural change. Their value depends on whether evaluation results are connected to feedback mechanisms that inform future policy and programme development. The input from patient organisations further reinforces this, pointing to a lack of systematic outcome measurement in several settings and underlining the importance of feedback loops and transparency mechanisms for understanding whether meaningful change has taken place because of patient input.

To address this gap, countries may consider:

- Developing national or organisational frameworks for monitoring PPIE activities and outcomes, building on existing international guidance on institutionalised social participation (9), and integrating these into routine oncology governance and evaluation structures.
- Defining a small set of core impact indicators (e.g. influence on policy decisions, care pathways, programme design) by combining qualitative and quantitative approaches, including patient-reported experience measures (PREMs), patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs), and process indicators.
- Ensuring that monitoring results are publicly reported and used to inform continuous improvement rather than solely for accountability purposes.
 - Integrating evaluation mechanisms early in programme design to enable consistent data collection.

Conclusion and Key Recommendations

In conclusion, the findings of this analysis demonstrate that while PPIE is widely recognised as an important principle of oncology governance across European countries, its implementation remains uneven, frequently relying on informal practices, limited resources, and discretionary institutional openness rather than systematic and enforceable frameworks.

The results from the survey, along with the inputs from patient organisations show that PPIE in cancer policy should reflect as a systematic inclusion of citizen and patient voices in the design, implementation and monitoring of cancer policies and services. This fits to the WHO framework of social participation (9) as well as earlier governance models which demonstrate that participation must move beyond consultation toward partnership and shared decision-making to produce sustainable system change (4).

In sum, the findings of this analysis, together with insights gained from the data collection process, will inform future evaluations of PPIE across stakeholder groups within the Penta helix and support ongoing capacity-building efforts in cancer governance — particularly within NCMHs.

Finally, the recommendations in **Table 3.** below are derived from the combined analysis of survey responses from public administration experts and qualitative reflections from patient organisations. Together, these perspectives highlight shared priorities, recurring structural gaps, and practical areas for policy action to strengthen meaningful, sustainable, and equitable participation in cancer governance.

Table 3. Key Recommendations in Context

Survey Area	Key Recommendation	Survey Findings Addressed	Patient Organisation Priorities Reflected
Area 1A – Strengthen Public Sector Capacities	1. Establish binding institutional frameworks for PPIE in public administration (guidelines/SOPs defining roles, responsibilities, minimum standards across oncology governance structures).	Heterogeneous formalisation; uneven rules in ministry advisory groups; SOPs for programme evaluation exist in 43.8% of countries and are absent in 43.8% , with 12.5% unable to answer. Formal representation in advisory structures reported by 62.5% of countries. Governance rules highly heterogeneous.	“Discretionary openness”, gaps in mandatory frameworks, and overestimation of institutionalisation by administrative accounts (“seat at the table” vs influence).
Area 1A – Strengthen Public Sector Capacities	2. Professionalise participation through systematic training for public administration staff, clinicians, and patient representatives (emphasizing on co-creation methods, facilitation, plain language, governance processes).	Publicly funded training exists for researchers in 43.8% of countries and for clinicians in 37.5% ; at least half report no training or uncertainty.	Lack of structured and adequately funded training on both sides; cultural gap where professionals lack participatory competence; “bottleneck” of too few trained patient reps.
Area 1B – NCCPs	3. Require structured patient/citizen representation in NCCP implementation bodies (mandated seats, clear remit,	Structured implementation involvement reported by 43.8% ; occasional involvement by 37.5% ; informal involvement by 18.8% . Participation primarily channelled via	Gap between formal inclusion and real influence; helps prevent participation being limited to ad hoc consultation and

Survey Area	Key Recommendation	Survey Findings Addressed	Patient Organisation Priorities Reflected	
		continuity through implementation and review).	patient organisations (93.3% of countries reporting involvement).	ensures continuity beyond plan drafting.
Area 2 – Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	4. Standardise accessibility measures for participation processes (hybrid/remote formats, plain language, barrier-free venues, reimbursement; consider childcare where feasible) through national guidance/SOPs.	Structured partnerships with underserved groups reported by 50% of countries; 25% report none; 25% unable to answer. Accessibility measures unevenly applied.	Practical feasibility (work/care duties), reimbursement gaps, technical language; participation often excludes those without flexible time or professional background.	
Area 2 – Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	5. Implement an explicit equity strategy for PPIE (structured outreach and partnerships with organisations representing underserved/underrepresented groups; ensure representation beyond well-organised cancer types).	Participation primarily occurs via established patient organisations; community advocates rarely involved; outreach practices inconsistently formalised.	Equity perspective is weak/non-systematic; addresses risk of representation limited to established groups and “missing voices.”	
Area 3 – Participation Influences	6. Introduce minimum transparency and feedback standards for consultations (who participated; what was submitted; what changed; publish summaries and	Internal monitoring reported by 25% of countries; public reporting by 56.3% ; no reporting by 25% . No	Gaps in transparency, accountability, and follow-through; need to show	

Survey Area	Key Recommendation	Survey Findings Addressed	Patient Organisation Priorities Reflected
Transparent Decisions	responses where feasible; provide feedback loops).	country reported audit or appeal mechanisms.	influence and avoid “box-ticking”.
Area 4 – Active Mechanisms in Policy/Legislation Development	7. Strengthen PPIE in later policy-cycle stages by moving from ad hoc to structured participation (implementation, monitoring/evaluation; clarify expected level of involvement per stage).	Participation common early, weak later; Participation most common in policy development (87.5%); programme design (62.5%); implementation (56.3%); monitoring/evaluation (43.8%). Later stages frequently informal or ad hoc.	Influence drops after early stages; late-stage engagement is limited and often not meaningful; need for co-creation and follow-through.
Area 5 – Adequate and Sustainable Resources	8. Establish predictable funding and compensation frameworks for PPIE (stable funding streams; reimbursement for travel/time; caregiving replacement; loss of earnings where relevant).	No sustainable resources reported by 43.8% of countries; remuneration policies exist in 31.3% ; 56.3% report none.	Gap between “claimed funding” and lived reality; voluntary engagement creates power imbalance; lack of stable funding undermines capacity, continuity, and diversity.
Area 6 – Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	9. Scale regular capacity-building and technical support for patient organisations (training, competence centres, advisory services,	Capacity initiatives often ad hoc; many countries report no technical support (56.25%); limited funding schemes absent in 50%	Call for structured competence-building and support; highlight over-reliance on a small group of highly committed

Survey Area	Key Recommendation	Survey Findings Addressed	Patient Organisation Priorities Reflected
Area 7 – Monitoring and Evaluation	<p>networking/knowledge exchange; link funding to capacity objectives).</p> <p>10. Establish core indicators and reporting mechanisms linking PPIE to decisions and outcomes (e.g. via use of PROMs/PREMs + process indicators; integrate into NCCP monitoring; ensure results lead to action).</p>	No country confirmed systematic tracking/reporting	<p>individuals; need to build a resilient ecosystem.</p> <p>Lack of outcome measurement and feedback loops</p>

References

1. European Commission. 2024 estimates of cancer cases and deaths in the EU (Factsheet). European Commission Joint Research Centre; 2026. Available from: https://ecis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2026-02/2026-02-10_A4_Factsheet_CancerEstimates24.pdf
2. Joint Research Centre. The latest EU cancer data: What is new? : European Commission; 2025 [cited 17.02.2025]. Available from: https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/jrc-news-and-updates/latest-eu-cancer-data-what-new-2025-12-17_en
3. Arnstein SR. A Ladder Of Citizen Participation. Journal of the American Institute of Planners. 1969;35(4):216-24.
4. Carman KL, Dardess P, Maurer M, Sofaer S, Adams K, Bechtel C, et al. Patient and family engagement: a framework for understanding the elements and developing interventions and policies. Health Aff (Millwood). 2013;32(2):223-31.
5. WHO. Social participation for universal health coverage: Technical paper. Genf: World Health Organization (WHO); 2023. Available from: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/igo/>
6. Bombard Y, Baker GR, Orlando E, Fancott C, Bhatia P, Casalino S, et al. Engaging patients to improve quality of care: a systematic review. Implement Sci. 2018;13(1):98.
7. Domecq JP, Prutsky G, Elraiyah T, Wang Z, Nabhan M, Shippee N, et al. Patient engagement in research: a systematic review. BMC Health Serv Res. 2014;14:89.
8. European Commission. EU Mission: Cancer — Implementation Plan. Brussels: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation; 2021.
9. WHO. Social participation for universal health coverage, health and well being (WHA77/ R2). Genf: World Health Organization (WHO); 2024. Available from: https://apps.who.int/gb/ebwha/pdf_files/WHA77/A77_R2-en.pdf
10. OECD. Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions: Catching the Deliberative Wave. Paris: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Publishing; 2020. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1787/339306da-en>
11. Zimba O, Gasparyan AY. Designing, Conducting, and Reporting Survey Studies: A Primer for Researchers. J Korean Med Sci. 2023;38(48):e403.

ANNEX – Completed Survey responses

Survey Template

Survey on Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) in Cancer Policy and Governance: Exploring Current Practices in Public Administration

Thank you for taking the time to contribute to this survey on Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) in oncology. This Survey was designed in the framework of the EU-project: ECHO S - Establishing of Cancer Mission Hubs: Networks and Synergies, Work Package 6 (Communication, Dissemination and Citizen Engagement), Task 6.2 focused on citizen engagement in the mission on cancer.

The survey examines:

- **Capacity** – whether the enabling structures for PPIE are in place and resourced (e.g., laws, policies, budgets, roles, training).
- **Practice/Influence** – how participation is actually implemented and to what extent it shapes decisions and outcomes across the cancer pathway.

Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) for the purpose of this work is the following: it encompasses the systematic integration of patients, citizens, and communities into decision-making processes with or by them—across research, healthcare delivery, public administration, and policy. In the cancer context, PPIE means recognising people affected by cancer as active partners in shaping priorities, designing interventions, informing governance, and evaluating outcomes. It is grounded in principles of inclusivity, equity, and

transparency, aiming to redistribute power, strengthen democratic legitimacy, and ensure that systems and policies reflect the lived experiences, values, and needs of those they are meant to serve.

Who should respond

This survey builds on the [WHO Resolution on Social Participation in Health](#), which urges Member States to strengthen and sustain meaningful participation in decision-making. The framework has been **adapted** to oncology and PPIE within seven analysis areas, loosely based on the seven resolution measures.

The questionnaire is intended for **national experts in Cancer Policy** (e.g. ministries of health, cancer agencies, NCCP bodies, regulators/payers) who can provide a system-wide perspective. Respondents may consult additional colleagues with complementary expertise if needed before finalising answers.

Time commitment

Completing the questionnaire will take approximately **45 minutes**. Most questions are multiple choice, complemented by short comment boxes where you can provide examples, links, or explanations. Several, answer options require the input of sources/links for reliability and validity.

Confidentiality

Responses will be analysed **at country level. Individual names and organisations will not be published.**

Purpose

Your input will help consolidate a structured overview for a Maturity Map on PPIE in cancer across countries participating in ECHO S. The findings will feed into the EU-Horizon project: ***ECHO S - Establishing of Cancer Mission Hubs: Networks and Synergies*** (find more Information about the project here: [Homepage - ECHO S - Cancer Missions Hubs](#)) and support the development of resources for National Cancer Mission Hubs across Europe.

We greatly appreciate your time and expertise in helping us advance more inclusive, transparent, and effective cancer governance.

Please note: *The **Establishing of Cancer Mission Hubs: Networks and Synergies (ECHO S)** project was funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme. Grant Agreement N°: 101104587. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect*

those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

There are 36 questions in this survey

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	
Date submitted	
General Questions	
[1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	
[Other]	
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	
[Slightly important]	
[Moderately important]	
[Very important]	
[Extremely important]	
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	
[Training programmes for clinicians]	

[Training programmes for patient advocates]	
[Other (please specify)]	
[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	
[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	
[Monitoring and evaluation]	
[Other]	
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	
[Yes]	
[No]	
[Cannot answer]	
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	
[Other (please specify)]	
[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	
[Other]	
[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	

[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	
[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.	
[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]	
[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	
[Cannot answer / not sure]	
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	
<i>National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy</i>	
[15/16] Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	
[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	
[No]	
[Cannot answer]	
[17] Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	
[No]	
[Other]	
[18] If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	
[Patient Advocate]	
[Patient Organization Representative]	
[Patient Expert]	
[Community Advocate]	
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	
[Public / Policy Expert]	

[Other]	
[19] To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	
[Not at all]	
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	
[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	
[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	
[Other]	
[20] If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	
[Patient Advocate]	
[Patient Organization Representative]	
[Patient Expert]	
[Community Advocate]	
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	
[Public / Policy Expert]	
[Other]	
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	
<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	
[21] Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	
[Plain language]	
[Hybrid/remote]	
[Stipends/expenses]	
[Accessible venue/design]	
[Childcare]	
[Digital inclusion support]	
[Cannot answer]	
[Other]	
[22/23] At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	

[Specify the type of partnership]	
[No]	
[Cannot answer]	
Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	
<i>This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.</i>	
[24] Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	
[Internal only]	
[Public]	
[Other]	
[25] When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	
[Not published]	
[Published (only summary)]	
[Published with response]	
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	
[Other]	
[26] Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	
[Published on the institution's official website]	
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	
[Published as a press release or news article]	
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	
[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	
[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	
[Not systematically made public]	
[Other]	
Area 4 - Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	
<i>This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology — from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.</i>	
[27] To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)? 1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;	
[Identifying priorities]	

[Designing programmes/regulations]	
[Collecting input/evidence]	
[Analysing input/evidence]	
[Communicating results]	
[Implementing programmes]	
[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	
Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources	
<i>This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.</i>	
[28] Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?	
[None]	
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	
[Funds for accompanying research]	
[Funds for patient organisations]	
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	
[Other]	
[29/30] At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.	
[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	
[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	
[No — no such policy exists]	
[Cannot answer]	
Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	
<i>This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.</i>	
[31/33] Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	
[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	
[Technical support]	
[Funding schemes]	
[Other]	

[32] Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	
<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	
[34/35] Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	
[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	
[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	
[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	
[Don't know / Not applicable]	
[Other]	
[36] As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.	

Thank you for completing the Survey.

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.

Austria

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	47
Date submitted	12.01.2026
General Questions	
[1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	GÖG; BMASGPK
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	Austria
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	No
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	Yes
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	No
[Other]	No
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	No
[Slightly important]	No
[Moderately important]	Yes
[Very important]	No
[Extremely important]	No
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	Yes
	To our knowledge, there are some publicly funded or at least publicly supported training opportunities for researchers or people interested in PPIE in general in AT, LBG Open Innovation in Science

	general training and education materials and webinars (https://ois.lbg.ac.at/)
[Training programmes for clinicians]	Yes
	Vienna Cancer School: https://ccc.meduniwien.ac.at/cancerschool ÖKUSS: https://oekuss.at/kurs ; Weiterbildung in Patientenzentrierter Gesundheitskommunikation from the Ministry of Health: https://goeg.at/weiterbildung_p_kommunikation ; https://oekuss.at/kurs ; Weiterbildung in Patientenzentrierter Gesundheitskommunikation
[Training programmes for patient advocates]	Yes
[Other (please specify)]	No
[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	
[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	Yes
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	No
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	Yes
[Monitoring and evaluation]	No
[Other]	Yes
	Advising of the ministry of Health - via patient organisations as participants of official advisory boards in oncology (National Oncology Advisory Board, National Cancer Screening Committee)
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	No
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	Yes
	National Oncology Advisory Board, National Cancer Screening Committee
[Other (please specify)]	No

[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	No
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	Yes
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	No
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	No
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	No
[Other]	Yes
	There are two formal documents in health in general: 1) Standard recommendations for public engagement: https://oeffentlicherdienst.gv.at/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Standards_der_Oeffentlichkeitsbeteiligung_2008.pdf and 2) There is a Patient Charter which is an agreement between federal states and the government
[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	N/A
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	N/A
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	N/A
[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.	

[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]	No
[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	No
[Cannot answer / not sure]	Yes
	Several not formalised practices are in place such as the consultation of patient representatives for the National Cancer Plan. Further, there are some documents with general SOPs for PPIE in health that could be applied to oncology related activities such as the HTA Manual for development of quality standards: https://www.sozialministerium.at/dam/jcr:2360a104-0b75-4a0c-8b50-51ff63c2ab16/Methodenhandbuch_3.0.pdf
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	
<i>National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy</i>	
[15/16] Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	Yes
[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	2025
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[17] Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Other]	No
[18] If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	
[Patient Advocate]	Yes
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	Yes
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	Yes
[Other]	Yes
	Representatives of self-help groups
[19] To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	

[Not at all]	No
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	No
[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	No
[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	Yes
[Other]	No
[20] If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	
[Patient Advocate]	Yes
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	Yes
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	Yes
[Other]	No
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	
<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	
[21] Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	No
[Plain language]	No
[Hybrid/remote]	No
[Stipends/expenses]	No
[Accessible venue/design]	No
[Childcare]	No
[Digital inclusion support]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[Other]	No
[22/23] At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	Yes
[Specify the type of partnership]	There are some collaborations and funding activities such as the funding/support of some self-help organisations including oncology related groups
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No

Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	
<i>This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.</i>	
[24] Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	No
[Internal only]	No
[Public]	No
[Other]	Yes
	members of the advisory boards are publicly listed on the homepage of the ministry of health: https://www.sozialministerium.gv.at/-Themen/Gesundheit/Nicht-uebertragbare-Krankheiten/Krebs/Onkologiebeirat.html
[25] When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	
[Not published]	Yes
[Published (only summary)]	No
[Published with response]	No
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	No
[Other]	No
[26] Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	
[Published on the institution's official website]	No
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	No
[Published as a press release or news article]	No
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	No
[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	No
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	No
[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	No
[Not systematically made public]	Yes
[Other]	No
Area 4 -Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	
<i>This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology — from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.</i>	
[27] To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)?	

1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;	
[Identifying priorities]	4
[Designing programmes/regulations]	4
[Collecting input/evidence]	4
[Analysing input/evidence]	4
[Communicating results]	4
[Implementing programmes]	4
[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	4
Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources	
<i>This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.</i>	
[28] Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?	
[None]	No
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	Yes
	not specifically for oncology but for supporting self-help organisations and patient participation for example via ÖKUSS
[Funds for accompanying research]	Yes
	Support for organisations such as LBG OIS and research calls such as via the Cancer Mission Lab (LBG OIS).
[Funds for patient organisations]	Yes
	not specifically for oncology but for self-help organisations in general (including oncology).
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	No
[Other]	No
[29/30] At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.	
[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	No
[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	N/A
[No — no such policy exists]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	

This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.

[31/33] Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	
[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	Yes, regular initiatives supported by policy/legislation
[Technical support]	N/A
[Funding schemes]	Yes, regular initiatives supported by policy/legislation
[Other]	Yes, regular initiatives supported by policy/legislation
	A participation strategy for the healthcare system is currently being developed, financed by the Ministry of Health.
[32] Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
ÖKUSS, funded by the Ministry of Health and the national social health insurance, provides training and administrates funding for activities of self-help organisations.	
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	
<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	
[34/35] Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	No
[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	N/A
[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	No
[Don't know / Not applicable]	No
[Other]	The GÖG Project and Service Catalog lists the committees and their members; the GÖG's one-time 2023 survey of examples of patient involvement provides an overview of existing patient involvement processes: https://goeg.at/Beteiligung_Gesundheitssystem ; it remains to be determined whether patient

	involvement should be incorporated into the development of patient pathways (Future Health Lab/GÖG).
[36] As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.	
-	

Belgium

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	12
Date submitted	12.11.2025
General Questions	
[1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	Sciensano
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	Belgium
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	No
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	No
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	No
[Other]	Belgium
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	No
[Slightly important]	No
[Moderately important]	No
[Very important]	Yes
[Extremely important]	No
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	No
[Training programmes for clinicians]	No
[Training programmes for patient advocates]	No
[Other (please specify)]	No
[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	

[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	Yes
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	No
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	No
[Monitoring and evaluation]	Yes
[Other]	Yes
	Review of protocols
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	
[Yes]	No
[No]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	No
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	No
[Other (please specify)]	Yes
	X
[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	N/A
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	N/A
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	N/A
[Other]	N/A
[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	N/A
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	N/A
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	N/A

[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	N/A
[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.	
[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]	No
[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	Yes
[Cannot answer / not sure]	No
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	
<i>National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy</i>	
Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	N/A
[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	N/A
[No]	N/A
[Cannot answer]	N/A
Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	N/A
[No]	N/A
[Other]	N/A
If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	
[Patient Advocate]	N/A
[Patient Organization Representative]	N/A
[Patient Expert]	N/A
[Community Advocate]	N/A
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	N/A
[Public / Policy Expert]	N/A
[Other]	N/A
To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	

[Not at all]	N/A
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	Yes
[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	No
[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	No
[Other]	No
If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	
[Patient Advocate]	No
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	No
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	
<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	
Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	No
[Plain language]	No
[Hybrid/remote]	No
[Stipends/expenses]	No
[Accessible venue/design]	No
[Childcare]	No
[Digital inclusion support]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[Other]	Yes
	Not systematically
At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	No
[Specify the type of partnership]	-
[No]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	

This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.

Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	Yes
[Internal only]	No
[Public]	No
[Other]	No
When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	
[Not published]	No
[Published (only summary)]	Yes
[Published with response]	No
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	No
[Other]	No
Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	
[Published on the institution's official website]	No
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	No
[Published as a press release or news article]	No
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	No
[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	No
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	No
[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	No
[Not systematically made public]	No
[Other]	Yes
	It depends
Area 4 -Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	
<i>This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology – from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.</i>	
To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)?	
1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;	
[Identifying priorities]	2
[Designing programmes/regulations]	1
[Collecting input/evidence]	2
[Analysing input/evidence]	1

[Communicating results]	2
[Implementing programmes]	1
[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	2
Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources	
<i>This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.</i>	
Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?	
[None]	Yes
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	No
[Funds for accompanying research]	No
[Funds for patient organisations]	No
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	No
[Other]	No
At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.	
[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	No
[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	-
[No — no such policy exists]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	
<i>This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.</i>	
Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	
[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	Yes, ad hoc initiatives only
[Technical support]	-
[Funding schemes]	Yes, ad hoc initiatives only
[Other]	-
Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
https://patientexpertcenter.be/	
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	
<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	

Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	No
[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	Yes
[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	No
[Don't know / Not applicable]	No
[Other]	No
As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.	
-	

Croatia

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	23
Date submitted	26.11.2025
General Questions	
[1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	Croatian Institute of Public Health
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	Croatia
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	No
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	No
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	Yes
[Other]	No
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	No
[Slightly important]	No
[Moderately important]	No
[Very important]	Yes
[Extremely important]	No
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	Yes
	Participation is optional, and the types of education are different (one-day meetings, professional conferences, participation in international projects. Financing available through national institutions and EU funds: Croatian Science Foundation: https://hrzz.hr/)

	Agency for Mobility and EU Programmes (AMPEU): https://www.ampeu.hr/
[Training programmes for clinicians]	Yes
	Participation is optional, and the types of education are different (one-day meetings, professional conferences, participation in international projects. Financing available through national institutions and EU funds Croatian Science Foundation: https://hrzz.hr/ Agency for Mobility and EU Programmes (AMPEU): https://www.ampeu.hr/
[Training programmes for patient advocates]	Yes
	Participation is optional, and the types of education are different (one-day meetings, professional conferences, participation in international projects. Financing available through national institutions and EU funds National Foundation for Civil Society Development, available at: https://zaklada.civilnodrustvo.hr/
[Other (please specify)]	Uncertain
[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	
[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	Yes
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	Yes
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	Yes
[Monitoring and evaluation]	No
[Other]	No
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	Yes
	In the development of strategies and guidelines for the fight against cancer.
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	Yes

	For the adoption of national strategies, laws and implementation action plans
[Other (please specify)]	Yes
	Public consultation is conducted electronically and is mandatory when adopting key laws (on health care and health insurance) 140 25.11.2009 Kodeks savjetovanja sa zainteresiranom javnošću u postupcima donošenja zakona, drugih propisa i akata
[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	No
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	No
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	No
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	Yes
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	No
[Other]	No
[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	No
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	No
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	No
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	Yes
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	No
[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.	

[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]	Yes
	<p>Public consultation, Commissions and Working Groups organized at the national level (Ministry of Health): https://zdravstvo.gov.hr/savjetovanje-s-javnoscju/1475</p> <p>Plans for advisory activities are regularly and transparently published on the website of the Ministry of Health. Plan savjetodavnih aktivnosti MZ u 2025..pdf</p> <p>Action plan for the implementation of the National strategic framework against cancer for the period until 2025 Akcijski plan za provedbu Nacionalnog strateškog okvira protiv raka za razdoblje do 2025..pdf</p>
[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	No
[Cannot answer / not sure]	No
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	
<i>National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy</i>	
[15/16] Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	Yes
[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	2020
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[17] Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Other]	No
[18] If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	
[Patient Advocate]	No
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	Yes
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	Yes
[Public / Policy Expert]	Yes
[Other]	No

[19] To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	
[Not at all]	No
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	No
[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	No
[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	Yes
[Other]	No
[20] If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	
[Patient Advocate]	No/Yes
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	Yes
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	Yes
[Public / Policy Expert]	Yes
[Other]	No
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	
<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	
[21] Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	Yes
[Plain language]	Yes
[Hybrid/remote]	Yes
[Stipends/expenses]	Yes
[Accessible venue/design]	Yes
[Childcare]	Yes
[Digital inclusion support]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
[Other]	No
[22/23] At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	Yes
[Specify the type of partnership]	Examples of such groups are: Rare Tumor Patient Associations, Parent Associations of Pediatric

	Oncology Patients, Survivors of Malignant Diseases, etc. – participated in: National Strategic Framework Against Cancer until 2030 (Adopted by: Croatian Parliament; Date of adoption of the national strategy: 18.12.2020. Available at: /eli/sluzbeni/2020/141/2728
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	
<i>This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.</i>	
[24] Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	No
[Internal only]	No
[Public]	Yes
[Other]	No
[25] When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	
[Not published]	No
[Published (only summary)]	Yes
[Published with response]	No
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	No
[Other]	No
[26] Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	
[Published on the institution's official website]	Yes
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	Yes
[Published as a press release or news article]	Yes
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	Yes
[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	Yes
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	Yes
[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	Yes
[Not systematically made public]	No
[Other]	No
Area 4 -Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	
<i>This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology — from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.</i>	

[27] To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)? 1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;	
[Identifying priorities]	2
[Designing programmes/regulations]	4
[Collecting input/evidence]	3
[Analysing input/evidence]	3
[Communicating results]	5
[Implementing programmes]	5
[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	2
Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources	
<i>This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.</i>	
[28] Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?	
[None]	No
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	No
[Funds for accompanying research]	Yes
	Healthcare institutions and researchers often collaborate with patient organizations on research and projects.
[Funds for patient organisations]	Yes
	At the local/county/city level, budgets are provided to support the work of associations, or, for example, business premises are allocated for work for a symbolic fee or free of charge. The amounts are determined differently (at the local/city/county level) and are annually coordinated and publicly published on the websites of local governments.
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	No
[Other]	No
[29/30] At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.	
[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	Travel expenses and time compensation (employer consent) are supported

[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	Travel expenses and time compensation (the consent of the employer) are co-financed at the national level for the members of the working groups during the development of laws and regulations related to health care Instructions are available at: https://zdravstvo.gov.hr/savjetovanje-s-javnoscju/1475
[No — no such policy exists]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	
<i>This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.</i>	
[31/33] Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	
[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	Yes, regular initiatives supported by policy/legislation
[Technical support]	Yes, regular initiatives supported by policy/legislation
[Funding schemes]	Yes, regular initiatives supported by policy/legislation
[Other]	No
[32] Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
Patient associations, professional associations, civil society, are familiar with the processes of consultation and decision-making on healthcare and the possibility of participating in project activities. There is a National Agency (Agency for Mobility and Programs of the EU; AMPEU) that helps citizens and organizations to get involved in successful projects and get educated using European Union funds. Information available at: https://www.ampeu.hr/	
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	
<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	
[34/35] Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	No
[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	No

[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	Yes
	We don't have any developed indicators yet.
[Don't know / Not applicable]	No
[Other]	No
[36] As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.	
Health and Care	

Cyprus

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	36
Date submitted	04.12.2025
General Questions	
[1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	Cyprus Cancer Research Institute and University of Cyprus
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	Cyprus
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	No
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	No
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	Yes
[Other]	No
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	No
[Slightly important]	No
[Moderately important]	Yes
[Very important]	No
[Extremely important]	No
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	No
[Training programmes for clinicians]	No
[Training programmes for patient advocates]	Uncertain
[Other (please specify)]	Uncertain
[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	

[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	Yes
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	No
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	No
[Monitoring and evaluation]	No
[Other]	Open and public dialogue (including patients) takes place ad hoc and at various stages. For example, recently, for the development of the palliative care services in Cyprus, the Ministry of Health introduced a bill for comments to any interested party/body/individual, prior to submitting to the Parliament for voting.
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	Yes
	National Cancer Committee-appointed by the Ministry of Health with the aim of coordinating all cancer related services in the country through the establishment of the National Cancer Institute
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	Yes
	Ministry national committees for example the committee for rare diseases which includes rare cancers.
[Other (please specify)]	No
[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	No
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	Yes
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	Yes
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	No

[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	No
[Other]	No
[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	No
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	No
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	No
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	No
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	No
[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.	
[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]	No
[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	Yes
[Cannot answer / not sure]	No
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	
<i>National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy</i>	
[15/16] Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	Yes
[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	2019
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[17] Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	No
[No]	Yes
[Other]	No
[18] If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	

[Patient Advocate]	N/A
[Patient Organization Representative]	N/A
[Patient Expert]	N/A
[Community Advocate]	N/A
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	N/A
[Public / Policy Expert]	N/A
[Other]	N/A
[19] To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	
[Not at all]	No
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	Yes
[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	No
[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	No
[Other]	No
[20] If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	
[Patient Advocate]	Yes
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	No
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	
<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	
[21] Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	No
[Plain language]	No
[Hybrid/remote]	No
[Stipends/expenses]	No
[Accessible venue/design]	No
[Childcare]	No
[Digital inclusion support]	No
[Cannot answer]	No

[Other]	No
[22/23] At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	No
[Specify the type of partnership]	-
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	Yes
Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	
<i>This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.</i>	
[24] Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	No
[Internal only]	Yes
[Public]	No
[Other]	No
[25] When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	
[Not published]	No
[Published (only summary)]	No
[Published with response]	No
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	No
[Other]	Not done in a structured way.
[26] Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	
[Published on the institution's official website]	No
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	No
[Published as a press release or news article]	No
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	No
[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	No
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	No
[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	No
[Not systematically made public]	No
[Other]	No
Area 4 -Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	

This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology — from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.

[27] To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)?
1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;

[Identifying priorities]	3
[Designing programmes/regulations]	1
[Collecting input/evidence]	2
[Analysing input/evidence]	1
[Communicating results]	1
[Implementing programmes]	2
[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	1

Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources

This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.

[28] Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?

[None]	Yes
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	No
[Funds for accompanying research]	No
[Funds for patient organisations]	No
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	No
[Other]	No

[29/30] At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.

[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	No
[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	-
[No — no such policy exists]	No
[Cannot answer]	Yes

Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening

This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.

[31/33] Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	
[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	N/A
[Technical support]	N/A
[Funding schemes]	N/A
[Other]	N/A
[32] Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
There are underway some initiatives which aim to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organizations effective participation.	
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	
<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	
[34/35] Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	No
[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	No
[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	Yes
[Don't know / Not applicable]	No
[Other]	No
[36] As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.	
Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and civil society, and Industry	

Finland

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	34
Date submitted	03.12.2025
General Questions	
[1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	Finnish Cancer Center FICAN
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	Finland
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	No
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	No
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	Yes
[Other]	No
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	No
[Slightly important]	Yes
[Moderately important]	No
[Very important]	No
[Extremely important]	No
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	No
[Training programmes for clinicians]	No
[Training programmes for patient advocates]	Yes
	Optional participation in EUPATI Finland activities (study group meetings)
[Other (please specify)]	Uncertain

[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	
[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	Yes
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	Yes
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	No
[Monitoring and evaluation]	No
[Other]	No
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	No
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	Yes
	Reform of pharmaceutical legislation and other relevant legislative reforms.
[Other (please specify)]	No
[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	No
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	No
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	No
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	No
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	No
[Other]	I am not aware of any rules. Patient organisations are invited to relevant advisory groups at Ministry, but it is mostly ad hoc basis.
[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	N/A

[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	N/A
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	N/A
[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.	
[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]	No
[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	Yes
[Cannot answer / not sure]	No
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	
<i>National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy</i>	
[15/16] Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	Yes
[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	2025
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[17] Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Other]	No
[18] If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	
[Patient Advocate]	Yes
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	Yes
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	Yes
[Public / Policy Expert]	Yes
[Other]	No

[19] To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	
[Not at all]	No
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	No
[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	No
[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	No
[Other]	The Finnish Cancer Strategy was published 10 Nov 2025, and we are just starting to work with the implementation plan.
[20] If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	
[Patient Advocate]	N/A
[Patient Organization Representative]	N/A
[Patient Expert]	N/A
[Community Advocate]	N/A
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	N/A
[Public / Policy Expert]	N/A
[Other]	-
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	
<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	
[21] Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	No
[Plain language]	No
[Hybrid/remote]	Yes
[Stipends/expenses]	No
[Accessible venue/design]	No
[Childcare]	No
[Digital inclusion support]	No
[Cannot answer]	Yes
[Other]	No
[22/23] At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	No

[Specify the type of partnership]	-
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	Yes
Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	
<i>This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.</i>	
[24] Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	No
[Internal only]	No
[Public]	Yes
[Other]	No
[25] When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	
[Not published]	No
[Published (only summary)]	No
[Published with response]	Yes
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	No
[Other]	No
[26] Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	
[Published on the institution's official website]	No
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	No
[Published as a press release or news article]	No
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	No
[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	No
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	No
[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	No
[Not systematically made public]	No
[Other]	Published on Ministry of Justice's online consultation platform
Area 4 -Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	
<i>This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology — from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.</i>	
[27] To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)? 1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;	

[Identifying priorities]	4
[Designing programmes/regulations]	3
[Collecting input/evidence]	3
[Analysing input/evidence]	3
[Communicating results]	4
[Implementing programmes]	4
[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	4
Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources	
<i>This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.</i>	
[28] Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?	
[None]	No
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	No
[Funds for accompanying research]	No
[Funds for patient organisations]	No
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	No
[Other]	There are no specific funds for PPIE, but the activities are implemented as part of organisations' overall budget.
[29/30] At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.	
[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	Patient representatives usually receive a compensation for patient advisory group meetings at hospitals (oncology clinics)
[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	-
[No — no such policy exists]	Yes
	Patient organisation representatives participating in the Ministry's advisory groups do not receive any remuneration.
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	
<i>This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.</i>	

[31/33] Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	
[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	Yes, ad hoc initiatives only
[Technical support]	Yes, ad hoc initiatives only
[Funding schemes]	-
[Other]	Yes, ad hoc initiatives only
[32] Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
EUPATI Finland: https://fi.eupati.eu/ and ad hoc trainings for patient advisory group members organised e.g. by hospitals.	
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	
<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	
[34/35] Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	No
[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	Yes
[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	No
[Don't know / Not applicable]	No
[Other]	No
[36] As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.	
Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society,	

Germany

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	16
Date submitted	17.11.2025
General Questions	
1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	Innovation Fund at the Federal Joint Committee (G-BA)
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	Germany
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	No
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	Yes
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	No
[Other]	No
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	No
[Slightly important]	No
[Moderately important]	Yes
[Very important]	No
[Extremely important]	No
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	No
[Training programmes for clinicians]	No
[Training programmes for patient advocates]	Yes
	- Patient Expert Academy for Tumor Diseases (PEAK) --> https://nct.dkfz.de/en/patient-

	involvement/patient-expert-academy.html participation is optional; - different courses are offered
[Other (please specify)]	No
[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	
[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	No
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	Yes
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	Yes
[Monitoring and evaluation]	Yes
[Other]	Yes
	Research e.g. Consultation process for new research topics, in the selection process for founding of research projects
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	Yes
	With the aim of tackling the problem areas in cancer screening and cancer care even more intensively, coordination the activities of all those involved in cancer control more effectively, and promoting a goal-oriented approach, the National Cancer Plan (NCP) was initiated on June 16, 2008; a content-related and structural realignment took place on November 6, 2004. https://www.bundesgesundheitsministerium.de/themen/praevention/nationaler-krebsplan/der-nationale-krebsplan-stellt-sich-vor
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	Yes
	The National Decade against Cancer brings together numerous key players to work on ensuring effective cancer research, in which patients are closely involved and which offers them increasingly improved prospects. Launched by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research

	(BMBF) and scheduled to run for ten years, the alliance aims to mobilize people in Germany to address the topic of cancer research. At the same time, it is also designed to reinforce support for research itself. Innovations should receive more targeted support and be made available to patients faster. By joining forces, it is hoped that there will be fewer new cases, cancer will be diagnosed more quickly and that better treatments will be developed. https://www.dekade-gegen-krebs.de/en/home/home_node.html
[Other (please specify)]	Yes
	Research Founding Grands by Research Founding Grands by Federal Ministry of Health (https://www.bundesgesundheitsministerium.de/en/index.html), Federal Ministry of Research (https://www.bmftr.bund.de/EN/Home/home_node.html), Technology and Space or the Innovations Found (https://innovationsfonds.gba.de/foerderbekanntmachungen/)
[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	No
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	No
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	No
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	No
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	Yes
[Other]	No
[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	No
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	No
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	No

[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	Yes
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	No
[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.	
[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]	Yes
	In funding programmes of the National Decade against Cancer, patient experts are included with advisory function and review of scientific research projects with voting rights.
[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	No
[Cannot answer / not sure]	No
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	
<i>National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy</i>	
[15/16] Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	Yes
[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	2024
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[17] Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Other]	No
[18] If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	
[Patient Advocate]	Yes
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	Yes
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	No

[Other]	No
[19] To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	
[Not at all]	No
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	No
[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	No
[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	Yes
[Other]	No
[20] If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	
[Patient Advocate]	Yes
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	Yes
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	No
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	
<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	
[21] Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	No
[Plain language]	No
[Hybrid/remote]	Yes
[Stipends/expenses]	Yes
[Accessible venue/design]	Yes
[Childcare]	No
[Digital inclusion support]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[Other]	Yes
	The Federal Joint Committee (Gemeinsamer Bundesausschuss, G-BA) patient involvement specialist team is tasked with organisational and content support (Social Code Book V. Section 140f 2015d); this includes methodological and legal advice, help with consulting documents,

	organisation of meetings and support with the nomination procedures for patient representatives in the HTA process within the G-BA and Innovationd Found. Training is also provided by the G-BA Medical Consultancy Department. https://patientenvertretung.g-ba.de/en
[22/23] At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	No
[Specify the type of partnership]	-
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	Yes
Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	
<i>This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.</i>	
[24] Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	No
[Internal only]	Yes
[Public]	No
[Other]	No
[25] When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	
[Not published]	Yes
[Published (only summary)]	No
[Published with response]	No
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	No
[Other]	No
[26] Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	
[Published on the institution's official website]	No
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	No
[Published as a press release or news article]	No
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	No
[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	No
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	No

[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	No
[Not systematically made public]	Yes
[Other]	
Area 4 -Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	
<i>This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology – from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.</i>	
[27] To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)? 1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;	
[Identifying priorities]	4
[Designing programmes/regulations]	3
[Collecting input/evidence]	3
[Analysing input/evidence]	4
[Communicating results]	4
[Implementing programmes]	2
[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	2
Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources	
<i>This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.</i>	
[28] Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?	
[None]	No
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	No
[Funds for accompanying research]	No
[Funds for patient organisations]	Yes
	The promotion of self-help is a statutory task of the health insurance funds and their associations according to § 20h SGB V. Funding is provided for health-related self-help – these are self-help groups, self-help organisations and self-help contact points. Promotion is provided at 3 levels: federal level, state level and regional level (self-help groups). There are 2 types of funding at each level: Community funding across all types of health insurance companies is joint funding of self-help groups, self-help organisations and self-help contact points by the statutory health insurance funds and their associations. These self-help structures are subsidised institutionally in

	the sense of basic funding within the framework of lump-sum funding.
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	Yes
	Within the Federal Joint Committee (Gemeinsamer Bundesausschuss, G-BA) and the Innovations found staff and technical support is offered
[Other]	Yes
	Patient participation is legally mandated in research projects funded by the German Innovation Fund (and is initiated by the German Federal Government). Accordingly, all associated costs, such as those for personnel or equipment, can be included in the funding. (https://innovationsfonds.g-ba.de/foerderbekanntmachungen/-foerderbekanntmachung-neue-versorgungsformen-zum-themenspezifischen-bereich-zweistufig-lang.56)
[29/30] At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.	
[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	Yes
[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	in BMG, BMFTE, G-BA and Innovations Found context Daily allowances, loss of earnings and travel expenses can be claimed. https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/167842/acdddc88f0e1d279d1fa9d23259ba0ab/30-03e-data.pdf for travel expenses - https://innovationsfonds.g-ba.de/downloads/media/457/2025-06-20_Personalmittelsaetze-IF.pdf for calculation of loss of earnings or if staff will be included in founding
[No — no such policy exists]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	
<i>This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.</i>	
[31/33] Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	

[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	Yes, regular initiatives without formal policy basis
[Technical support]	No
[Funding schemes]	Yes, regular initiatives supported by policy/legislation
[Other]	No
[32] Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
- without formal policy basis --> Self-help groups independently offer further training in various areas. e.g. https://www.rheuma-liga.de/unser-einsatz/rheumaforschung/partizipative-forschung or https://www.rheuma-liga.de/fileadmin/public/main_domain/Dokumente/2016_Article_MitteilungenDerDRL.pdf - https://www.bag-selbsthilfe.de/informationen-fuer-selbsthilfe-aktive/qualifizierung	
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	
<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	
[34/35] Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	No
[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	No
[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	Yes
[Don't know / Not applicable]	No
[Other]	No
[36] As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.	
Patient Representatives and patient organisations for example: https://hausderkrebselbsthilfe.de/ ; https://www.bag-selbsthilfe.de/basisinformationen-in-anderen-sprachversionen/english-englisch or https://www.nakos.de/adressen/datenbanksuche/	

Hungary

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	32
Date submitted	02.12.2025
General Questions	
[1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	Deputy State Secretariat for Health, Ministry of Interior
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	Magyarország
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	Yes
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	No
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	No
[Other]	No
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	No
[Slightly important]	No
[Moderately important]	No
[Very important]	Yes
[Extremely important]	No
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	No
[Training programmes for clinicians]	No
[Training programmes for patient advocates]	No
[Other (please specify)]	No

[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	
[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	Yes
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	No
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	No
[Monitoring and evaluation]	No
[Other]	No
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	
[Yes]	No
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	Yes
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	No
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	No
[Other (please specify)]	Yes
	-
[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	N/A
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	N/A
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	N/A
[Other]	No
[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	N/A

[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	N/A
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	N/A
<p>[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.</p>	
<p>[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]</p>	<p>A vizsgálati és terápiás eljárási rendek kidolgozásának, szerkesztésének, valamint az ezeket érintő szakmai egyeztetések lefolytatásának egységes szabályairól szóló 18/2013. (III. 5.) EMMI rendelet 7. § (1) bekezdése szerint az irányelvet fejlesztő csoportba tanácskozási joggal rendelkező tagokat (többek közt betegeket és betegszervezeteket) delegálhat a 6. § (1) bekezdése szerint • az egészségügyért felelős miniszter, • az adott szakma képviselőjében az egészségügyi szakmai kollégium tagozata, • az Országos Kórházi Főigazgatóság, • az országos tisztifőorvos, • a Nemzeti Egészségbiztosítási Alapkezelő, • a Nemzeti Betegfórum, • más, az egészségügyi ágazatban működő, a témakör szerint érintett szervezet. [1] Példa a betegszervezet delegálására tanácskozási joggal. A Belügyminisztérium egészségügyi szakmai irányelve a prosztatatarák komplex diagnosztikájáról és ellátásáról című egészségügyi szakmai irányelvfejlesztésbe tanácskozási joggal részt vett a Magyar Rákellenes Liga. [2] Forrás: [1] 18/2013. (III. 5.) EMMI rendelet a vizsgálati és terápiás eljárási rendek kidolgozásának, szerkesztésének, valamint az ezeket érintő szakmai egyeztetések lefolytatásának egységes szabályairól, elérhetőség: https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=a1300018.emm [2] A Belügyminisztérium egészségügyi szakmai irányelve a prosztatatarák komplex diagnosztikájáról és ellátásáról, elérhetőség: https://www.kozlonyok.hu/kozlonyok/-Kozlonyok/6/PDF/2025/9.pdf</p>

[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	No
[Cannot answer / not sure]	No
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	
<i>National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy</i>	
[15/16] Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	Yes
[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	1993
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[17] Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Other]	No
[18] If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	
[Patient Advocate]	No
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	Yes
[Other]	No
[19] To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	
[Not at all]	No
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	No
[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	Yes
[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	No
[Other]	No
[20] If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	
[Patient Advocate]	Yes
[Patient Organization Representative]	No
[Patient Expert]	No

[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	Yes
[Other]	No
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	
<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	
[21] Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	Yes
[Plain language]	No
[Hybrid/remote]	No
[Stipends/expenses]	No
[Accessible venue/design]	Yes
[Childcare]	No
[Digital inclusion support]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[Other]	No
[22/23] At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	Yes
[Specify the type of partnership]	Health visitor nurses in health care serve in underserved areas organized by the National Directorate General for Hospitals (OKFŐ)
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	
<i>This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.</i>	
[24] Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	No
[Internal only]	No
[Public]	Yes
[Other]	No
[25] When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	

[Not published]	No
[Published (only summary)]	Yes
[Published with response]	No
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	No
[Other]	No
[26] Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	
[Published on the institution's official website]	No
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	No
[Published as a press release or news article]	No
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	No
[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	No
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	No
[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	Yes
[Not systematically made public]	No
[Other]	No
Area 4 -Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	
<i>This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology – from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.</i>	
[27] To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)? 1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;	
[Identifying priorities]	4
[Designing programmes/regulations]	3
[Collecting input/evidence]	3
[Analysing input/evidence]	3
[Communicating results]	-
[Implementing programmes]	5
[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	4
Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources	
<i>This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.</i>	
[28] Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?	
[None]	No
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	No

[Funds for accompanying research]	No
[Funds for patient organisations]	No
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	No
[Other]	No
[29/30] At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.	
[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	No
[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	-
[No — no such policy exists]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	
<i>This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.</i>	
[31/33] Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	
[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	N/A
[Technical support]	N/A
[Funding schemes]	N/A
[Other]	N/A
[32] Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
-	
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	
<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	
[34/35] Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	No

[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	No
[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	No
[Don't know / Not applicable]	No
[Other]	-
[36] As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.	
-	

Ireland

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	18
Date submitted	20.11.2025
General Questions	
[1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	HSE-NCCP
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	Ireland
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	Yes
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	No
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	No
[Other]	No
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	No
[Slightly important]	No
[Moderately important]	No
[Very important]	No
[Extremely important]	Yes
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	Yes
	Public and Patient Involvement (PPI) refers to the active collaboration between researchers and individuals with lived experiences, patients, carers, service users, and members of the public, throughout the research process. This partnership encompasses the planning,

	design, execution, and dissemination phases of research, ensuring that studies are conducted with or by the public, rather than to, about, or for them. https://hseresearch.ie/patient-and-public-involvement-in-research/
[Training programmes for clinicians]	Yes
	PPI Ignite Network Ireland PPI Ignite Network Ireland: The PPI Ignite Network is funded by the Health Research Board and Irish Research Council and aims to promote excellence and innovation in PPI. It is a partnership between 7 lead universities and national partners including IPPOSI, Research Charities, and HSE. It is a useful source of information for researchers and public and patient contributors to research. https://ppinetwork.ie/
[Training programmes for patient advocates]	Yes
	PPI Ignite Network Ireland PPI Ignite Network Ireland: The PPI Ignite Network is funded by the Health Research Board and Irish Research Council and aims to promote excellence and innovation in PPI. It is a partnership between 7 lead universities and national partners including IPPOSI, Research Charities, and HSE. It is a useful source of information for researchers and public and patient contributors to research. https://ppinetwork.ie/
[Other (please specify)]	Uncertain
[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	
[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	Yes
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	Yes
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	Yes
[Monitoring and evaluation]	Yes
[Other]	No
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	Yes

	https://www.hse.ie/eng/services/list/5/cancer/profinfo/survivorship-programme/nccp-directory-of-community-cancer-support-centres-and-services.pdf
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	Yes
	https://www.gov.ie/en/department-of-health/organisation-information/cancer-patient-advisory-committee/
[Other (please specify)]	Yes
	https://www.ucd.ie/patientvoicecancer/about/steeringcommittee/
[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	No
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	No
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	No
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	Yes
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	Yes
[Other]	No
[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	No
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	No
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	No
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	Yes
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	Yes
[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting,	

adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.	
[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]	Yes
	https://assets.gov.ie/static/documents/cancer-patient-advisory-committee-terms-of-reference.pdf
[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	No
[Cannot answer / not sure]	No
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	
<i>National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy</i>	
[15/16] Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	Yes
[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	2017
[No]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
[17] Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Other]	No
[18] If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	
[Patient Advocate]	Yes
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	Yes
[Public / Policy Expert]	Yes
[Other]	No
[19] To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	
[Not at all]	No
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	No
[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	No

[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	Yes
[Other]	No
[20] If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	
[Patient Advocate]	Yes
[Patient Organization Representative]	No
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	Yes
[Other]	No
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	
<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	
[21] Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	No
[Plain language]	Yes
[Hybrid/remote]	Yes
[Stipends/expenses]	No
[Accessible venue/design]	Yes
[Childcare]	No
[Digital inclusion support]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[Other]	No
[22/23] At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	Yes
[Specify the type of partnership]	https://www.hse.ie/eng/services/list/5/cancer/profinfo/community%20cancer%20support%20centres.html https://hseresearch.ie/patient-and-public-involvement-in-research/#Training-and-Support-Resources https://ppinetwork.ie/
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	

<i>This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.</i>	
[24] Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	No
[Internal only]	Yes
[Public]	Yes
[Other]	No
[25] When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	
[Not published]	No
[Published (only summary)]	Yes
[Published with response]	Yes
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	No
[Other]	No
[26] Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	
[Published on the institution's official website]	No
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	Yes
[Published as a press release or news article]	Yes
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	Yes
[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	Yes
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	Yes
[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	Yes
[Not systematically made public]	No
[Other]	No
Area 4 -Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	
<i>This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology — from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.</i>	
[27] To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)? 1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;	
[Identifying priorities]	4
[Designing programmes/regulations]	4
[Collecting input/evidence]	4
[Analysing input/evidence]	4
[Communicating results]	4

[Implementing programmes]	4
[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	4
Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources	
<i>This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.</i>	
[28] Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?	
[None]	No
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	Yes
	https://hseresearch.ie/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Guide-no-8a-Costing-and-Budgeting-for-Patient-and-Public-Involvement-in-Health-Research.pdf
[Funds for accompanying research]	Yes
	https://hseresearch.ie/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Guide-no-8a-Costing-and-Budgeting-for-Patient-and-Public-Involvement-in-Health-Research.pdf
[Funds for patient organisations]	Yes
	https://hseresearch.ie/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Guide-no-8a-Costing-and-Budgeting-for-Patient-and-Public-Involvement-in-Health-Research.pdf
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	Yes
	https://hseresearch.ie/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Guide-no-8a-Costing-and-Budgeting-for-Patient-and-Public-Involvement-in-Health-Research.pdf
[Other]	No
[29/30] At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.	
[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	Yes
	https://www2.healthservice.hse.ie/organisation/national-pppgs/policy-on-the-reimbursement-of-expenses-for-patient-and-service-user-partners/
[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	https://www2.healthservice.hse.ie/organisation/national-pppgs/policy-on-the-reimbursement-of-expenses-for-patient-and-service-user-partners/ HSE National Policy

	on Reimbursement of Expenses for Patient and Service User Partners (https://www2.healthservice.hse.ie/files/225/)
[No — no such policy exists]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	
<i>This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.</i>	
[31/33] Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	
[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	Yes, regular initiatives supported by policy/legislation
[Technical support]	Yes, regular initiatives supported by policy/legislation
[Funding schemes]	Yes, regular initiatives supported by policy/legislation
[Other]	Yes, regular initiatives supported by policy/legislation
[32] Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
https://www.carealliance.ie/funding https://www.hse.ie/eng/services/list/5/cancer/profinfo/survivorship-programme/nccp-directory-of-community-cancer-support-centres-and-services.pdf	
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	
<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	
[34/35] Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	Yes
	https://www.hrb.ie/funding/responsible-research-assessment/public-and-patient-involvement-in-research/ https://ppinetwork.ie/ https://hrcdc.ie/your-data/public-and-patient-involvement-and-the-hrcdc/
[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	Yes
[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	No
[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	No
[Don't know / Not applicable]	No
[Other]	No

[36] As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.

Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society

Italy

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	24
Date submitted	26.11.2025
General Questions	
[1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	Regional Foundation for Biomedical Research - Fondazione Regionale per la Ricerca Biomedica
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	Italia
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	Yes
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	No
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	No
[Other]	No
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	No
[Slightly important]	No
[Moderately important]	No
[Very important]	No
[Extremely important]	Yes
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	Yes
	At the Italian level, we note the APENet (Associazione "Rete italiana degli Atenei ed Enti di Ricerca per il Public Engagement") https://www.apenetwork.it/ APENet acts as a network to promote and coordinate exchange activities between the academic community and society,

	overcoming the idea of a closed system. Several Italian Universities that are members of that association organize events and seminars on the subject (ex: LA NOTTE DEI RICERCATORI https://www.mur.gov.it/it/comunicazione/eventi/notte-europea-dei-ricercatori-2025) . All activities are optional.
[Training programmes for clinicians]	Yes
	We underline the course "Comunicazione della scienza e Public Engagement" https://ums.unife.it/offerta-formativa/comunicazione-della-scienza-e-public-engagement). The course is optional.
[Training programmes for patient advocates]	Uncertain
[Other (please specify)]	No
[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	
[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	Yes
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	Yes
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	Yes
[Monitoring and evaluation]	Yes
[Other]	No
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	
[Yes]	No
[No]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	Yes
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	Yes
[Other (please specify)]	Yes
	N:A
[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	Yes

[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	No
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	No
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	No
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	No
[Other]	No
[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	Yes
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	No
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	No
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	No
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	No
[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.	
[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]	No
[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	Yes
[Cannot answer / not sure]	No
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	
<i>National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy</i>	
[15/16] Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	Yes

[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	2023
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[17] Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Other]	No
[18] If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	
[Patient Advocate]	Yes
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	No
[19] To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	
[Not at all]	No
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	Yes
[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	No
[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	No
[Other]	No
[20] If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	
[Patient Advocate]	No
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	No
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	
<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	

[21] Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	No
[Plain language]	No
[Hybrid/remote]	Yes
[Stipends/expenses]	No
[Accessible venue/design]	No
[Childcare]	No
[Digital inclusion support]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
[Other]	No
[22/23] At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	Yes
[Specify the type of partnership]	Reti Oncologiche/cancer networks: https://www.regione.lombardia.it/wps/portal/-istituzionale/HP/DettaglioRedazionale/servizi-einformazioni/Enti-e-Operatori/sistema-welfare/reti-di-patologia-e-di-servizi/rete-oncologica/reteoncologica
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	
<i>This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.</i>	
[24] Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	No
[Internal only]	No
[Public]	Yes
[Other]	No
[25] When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	
[Not published]	No
[Published (only summary)]	Yes
[Published with response]	No
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	No
[Other]	No
[26] Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	

[Published on the institution's official website]	Yes
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	Yes
[Published as a press release or news article]	No
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	No
[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	Yes
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	No
[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	No
[Not systematically made public]	No
[Other]	No
Area 4 -Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	
<i>This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology — from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.</i>	
[27] To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)? 1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;	
[Identifying priorities]	2
[Designing programmes/regulations]	2
[Collecting input/evidence]	2
[Analysing input/evidence]	2
[Communicating results]	1
[Implementing programmes]	2
[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	2
Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources	
<i>This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.</i>	
[28] Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?	
[None]	No
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	Yes
	Considering Lombardy Region calls for proposals (https://www.openinnovation.regione.lombardia.it/it/bandi-e-sperimentazioni/ricerca-e-innova)

[Funds for accompanying research]	Yes
	Considering Lombardy Region calls for proposals (https://frrb.it/bandi-main/)
[Funds for patient organisations]	No
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	No
[Other]	No
[29/30] At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.	
[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	No
[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	-
[No — no such policy exists]	Yes
	at the moment not planned
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	
<i>This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.</i>	
[31/33] Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	
[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	Yes, regular initiatives without formal policy basis
[Technical support]	Yes, regular initiatives without formal policy basis
[Funding schemes]	-
[Other]	-
[32] Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
L'APENet (Associazione "Rete italiana degli Atenei ed Enti di Ricerca per il Public Engagement") https://www.apenetwork.it/	
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	
<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	
[34/35] Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	No

[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	No
[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	No
[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	Yes
[Don't know / Not applicable]	No
[Other]	No
[36] As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.	
Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia	

The Netherlands

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	41
Date submitted	05.12.2025
General Questions	
[1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	The hub of the Netherlands Cancer Collective
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	the Netherlands
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	No
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	Yes
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	No
[Other]	No
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	No
[Slightly important]	No
[Moderately important]	No
[Very important]	Yes
[Extremely important]	No
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	Yes
	There are indeed publicly funded and structured support/training opportunities for researchers to practice. These vary widely in format and duration — from short advice/coaching to long-term training programmes (e.g. 14-month EUPATI cohort). publicly

	<p>supported PPIE training opportunities exist for researchers in the Netherlands.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · INVOLV (formerly PGOsupport) provides training, coaching and advisory support for researchers, focused on strengthening meaningful participation with patients and civil society. https://www.involv.nl · EUPATI NL, coordinated by INVOLV, offers a structured 14-month training programme preparing participants (including researchers collaborating with patient advocates) for co-creation in medicines development and health research. https://www.involv.nl/eupati-nederland-opleiding · ZonMw integrates patient involvement as an assessment criterion or requirement in many of its research funding programmes and provides guidance, tools and workshops for researchers to implement PPIE effectively. <p>Source: https://www.zonmw.nl/nl/artikel/patientenparticipatie-onderzoek-weten-wat-er-echt-toe-doet/</p> <p>Participation: optional, depending on programme Formats: workshops, coaching, online modules, long-term programmes</p>
[Training programmes for clinicians]	Uncertain
[Training programmes for patient advocates]	Yes
	<p>In the Netherlands, publicly funded training programmes for patient advocates do exist. The largest provider is INVOLV (https://www.involv.nl), funded by the Ministry of Health (VWS). INVOLV offers structured training, coaching and advisory support for patient advocates, aimed at strengthening skills in participation, co-creation, governance, policy involvement and research collaboration.</p> <p>Format & duration: workshops (2–4 hours), online modules, multi-session training programmes, and longer-term coaching trajectories depending on organisational needs. Participation is optional. In the Netherlands, there are additional publicly supported training opportunities for experts by experience (ervaringsdeskundigen) in oncology who contribute to PPIE activities such as peer support, care improvement and advisory roles.</p> <p>The Associate Degree “Ervaringsdeskundigheid in Zorg en Welzijn” trains experts by experience to participate structurally in care, policy and service design. The programme is co-funded by KWF Kankerbestrijding,</p>

	which covers tuition fees for eligible ervaringsdeskundigen. Format: two-year work-and-study programme; participation is optional. https://www.kwf.nl/ervaringsdeskundig-professional
[Other (please specify)]	Yes
	Clinicians have access to publicly supported training on shared decision-making, mainly through the national programme Uitkomstgerichte zorg (supported by the Ministry of Health). This includes the e-learning “De kern van Samen Beslissen”, consisting of short modules for medical specialists, trainees and other professionals (optional participation). https://kennisplatform.uitkomstgerichte zorg.nl/-onderwijs/onderwijsaanbod/samen-beslissen Although these materials support patient-centred care, we do not have a national, publicly funded PPIE-specific training programme for clinicians.
[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	
[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	Yes
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	Yes
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	Yes
[Monitoring and evaluation]	Yes
[Other]	No
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	Yes
	advise on quality of cancer care, concentration and regional organisation of oncology services.
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	No
[Other (please specify)]	No

[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	N/A
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	N/A
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	N/A
[Other]	N/A
[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	No
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	No
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	No
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	Yes
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	No
[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.	
[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]	No
[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	Yes
	There are no legal requirements, ministerial guidelines or national SOPs in the Netherlands that mandate PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation or evaluation).

	Mandatory patient involvement does exist in guideline development and quality standards (broader healthcare sector), but this is regulated via professional frameworks, not oncology-specific national policy SOPs.
[Cannot answer / not sure]	No
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	
<i>National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy</i>	
[15/16] Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	Yes
[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	2023
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[17] Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Other]	No
[18] If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	
[Patient Advocate]	Yes
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	Yes
[Community Advocate]	Yes
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	No
[19] To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	
[Not at all]	No
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	No
[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	Yes
[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	No
[Other]	No
[20] If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	

[Patient Advocate]	Yes
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	Yes
[Community Advocate]	Yes
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	Yes
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	No
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	
<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	
[21] Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	Yes
[Plain language]	Yes
[Hybrid/remote]	No
[Stipends/expenses]	No
[Accessible venue/design]	Yes
[Childcare]	No
[Digital inclusion support]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[Other]	Yes
	Other measures—including hybrid/remote participation, childcare, digital inclusion support, and stipends—are used in practice but not covered by systematic or legally mandated SOPs for PPIE in oncology or broader public-administration involvement. Therefore, they cannot be selected as “systematically applied
[22/23] At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	Yes
[Specify the type of partnership]	At the public administration level in the Netherlands, there are structured partnerships and outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and underrepresented groups. · Pharos, the national centre of expertise on health disparities, works structurally with policymakers, public institutions and professionals at national, regional and local levels to improve health equity for groups such as migrants, people with low literacy and low

	<p>socioeconomic status. https://www.pharos.nl/over-pharos/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · The Alliance for Health Literacy (Alliantie Gezondheidsvaardigheden) brings together public bodies, civil-society organisations and healthcare actors to support people with limited health literacy. https://www.gezondheidsvaardigheden.nl/over-ons/ · National programmes on digital inclusion involve structured collaboration between the Dutch government, municipalities, libraries and civil-society partners to reduce digital exclusion of vulnerable groups. https://www.digitaleoverheid.nl/overzicht-van-alle-onderwerpen/digitale-inclusie/
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	
<i>This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.</i>	
[24] Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	No
[Internal only]	Yes
[Public]	Yes
[Other]	No
[25] When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	
[Not published]	No
[Published (only summary)]	No
[Published with response]	No
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	No
[Other]	Yes
	<p>Our entity is not a standalone organisation, but a hub in a collaborative network the Dutch Netherlands Cancer Collective (Nederlands Kanker Collectief). We do not conduct formal public consultations in the governmental sense. While participation in Acceleration Teams and action plans is documented and publicly listed (e.g., participating organisations), these are work structures, not public consultations, and therefore no formal publication of consultation results, summaries, responses or audit procedures exists.</p>
[26] Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	

[Published on the institution's official website]	Yes
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	No
[Published as a press release or news article]	No
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	Yes
[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	Yes
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	Yes
[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	Yes
[Not systematically made public]	No
[Other]	Yes
	While we do not conduct formal public consultations, the outcomes of our collaborative and participatory activities are regularly shared through several channels. Results and updates are published on the Netherlands Cancer Collective's website, communicated directly to participants and stakeholder organisations, and are often presented at national meetings, workshops or other public events. In addition, some outputs are shared through newsletters or social media as part of regular dissemination efforts.
Area 4 -Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	
<i>This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology — from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.</i>	
<p>[27] To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)? 1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;</p>	
[Identifying priorities]	4
[Designing programmes/regulations]	3
[Collecting input/evidence]	5
[Analysing input/evidence]	2
[Communicating results]	4
[Implementing programmes]	3
[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	5
Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources	
<i>This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.</i>	
<p>[28] Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?</p>	

[None]	No
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	No
[Funds for accompanying research]	No
[Funds for patient organisations]	No
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	No
[Other]	Yes
	There is no public evidence of sustainable, dedicated public-sector resources (budget, staffing, technical support) allocated specifically to ensure effective PPIE in oncology-related activities in the Netherlands. While patient organisations may receive general funding through various sources, these funds are not earmarked for PPIE in oncology policy or programme development
[29/30] At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.	
[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	No
[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	-
[No — no such policy exists]	Yes
	There is no national or regional policy regulating remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors in oncology-related policy or programme activities. Existing legal frameworks, such as the Wmcz 2018, apply only to client councils within care institutions, not to national PPIE processes
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	
<i>This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.</i>	
[31/33] Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	
[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	Yes, regular initiatives without formal policy basis
[Technical support]	Yes, regular initiatives without formal policy basis
[Funding schemes]	Yes, regular initiatives without formal policy basis
[Other]	No

[32] Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
For the the answers provided for Question 32 see earlier responses regarding PPIE training, technical support and funding. (Strengthen public sector capacities)	
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	
<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	
[34/35] Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	No
[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	No
[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	No
[Don't know / Not applicable]	No
[Other]	Neither our collaboration nor affiliated entities within the Netherlands Cancer Collective systematically track or report outcome indicators that link PPIE to decision-making effects (e.g., policy adjustments, resource allocation, access or equity impacts). While patient input is used in agenda-setting and programme development, there is no published framework in the Netherlands that measures or reports the downstream effects of PPIE on oncology policy or programme outcomes, other than the outcome of the action plans of the Netherland Cancer Agenda
[36] As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.	
In my daily work within the Netherlands Cancer Collective and the implementation of the Netherlands Cancer Agenda, we collaborate most frequently with stakeholders from Health and Care, followed by Knowledge and Academia and Citizens and Civil Society.	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health and Care: This includes comprehensive cancer centres, hospitals, oncology networks, IKNL, PZNL and prevention partners involved in programme development and implementation. • Knowledge and Academia: Collaboration with universities, research institutes and experts contributing evidence, guidelines, data analysis and thematic knowledge. 	

- Citizens and Civil Society: Regular interaction with patient organisations (e.g., NFK and affiliated patient groups), experiential experts and stakeholders representing the patient voice in action plans and working groups.
- Industry: Collaboration occurs far less frequently, and typically only when relevant to specific innovation or implementation projects.

Norway

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	10
Date submitted	10.11.2025
General Questions	
[1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	Norwegian Ministry of Health and Care Services
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	Norway
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	Yes
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	No
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	No
[Other]	No
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	No
[Slightly important]	No
[Moderately important]	No
[Very important]	Yes
[Extremely important]	No
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	Uncertain
[Training programmes for clinicians]	Uncertain
[Training programmes for patient advocates]	Uncertain
[Other (please specify)]	Uncertain
[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	

[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	Yes
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	No
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	Yes
[Monitoring and evaluation]	Yes
[Other]	No
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	
[Yes]	No
[No]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	No
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	No
[Other (please specify)]	Yes
	We have no formalised structure for this in Norway, but user- and patient organisations shall always participate in this kind of work. .
[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	N/A
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	N/A
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	N/A
[Other]	N/A
[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	N/A
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	N/A

[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	N/A
[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.	
[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]	No
[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	Yes
	Norway practise user- and patient involvement, but this is not formalised. The users and patient organisations are always invited to participate, but how this is done, depends on what kind of product that shall be elaborated. See the website Helsedirektoratet.
[Cannot answer / not sure]	No
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	
<i>National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy</i>	
[15/16] Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	Yes
[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	2025
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[17] Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Other]	No
[18] If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	
[Patient Advocate]	No
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes

[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	No
[19] To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	
[Not at all]	No
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	No
[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	No
[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	Yes
[Other]	No
[20] If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	
[Patient Advocate]	No
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	No
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	
<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	
[21] Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	No
[Plain language]	No
[Hybrid/remote]	No
[Stipends/expenses]	No
[Accessible venue/design]	No
[Childcare]	No
[Digital inclusion support]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[Other]	Yes

	There is established a structures partnership in relation to the Norwegian Cancer Strategy 2025-2035. This include all types of cancer.
[22/23] At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	No
[Specify the type of partnership]	-
[No]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	
<i>This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.</i>	
[24] Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	Yes
[Internal only]	No
[Public]	No
[Other]	No
[25] When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	
[Not published]	Yes
[Published (only summary)]	No
[Published with response]	No
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	No
[Other]	No
[26] Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	
[Published on the institution's official website]	No
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	No
[Published as a press release or news article]	No
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	No
[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	No
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	No
[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	No
[Not systematically made public]	Yes
[Other]	No

Area 4 -Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	
<i>This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology — from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.</i>	
[27] To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)? 1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;	
[Identifying priorities]	3
[Designing programmes/regulations]	3
[Collecting input/evidence]	4
[Analysing input/evidence]	2
[Communicating results]	1
[Implementing programmes]	2
[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	2
Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources	
<i>This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.</i>	
[28] Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?	
[None]	Yes
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	No
[Funds for accompanying research]	No
[Funds for patient organisations]	No
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	No
[Other]	No
[29/30] At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.	
[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	No
[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	-
[No — no such policy exists]	Yes
	The rules for remuneration for travel costs applies generally to all who travel in service at the state's expense. There is no specific remuneration or reimbursement for patient ore public contributors.

[Cannot answer]	No
Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	
<i>This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.</i>	
[31/33] Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	
[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	No
[Technical support]	No
[Funding schemes]	No
[Other]	Yes
	Yes, regular initiatives supported by policy/legislation
[32] Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
Norway has no specific arrangement for this concerning cancer.	
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	
<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	
[34/35] Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	No
[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	No
[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	Yes
[Don't know / Not applicable]	No
[Other]	No
[36] As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.	
Health and Care Knowledge and Academia We do not work with these stakeholder as a part of our daily work, but we regularly collaborate most with these two stakeholders.	

Portugal

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	49
Date submitted	28.01.2026
General Questions	
[1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	AICIB
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	Portugal
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	Yes
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	No
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	No
[Other]	No
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	No
[Slightly important]	No
[Moderately important]	No
[Very important]	Yes
[Extremely important]	No
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	Yes
	The trainings are optional and the format and duration of the trainings are adapted to each need identified (not time-defined/periodic).
[Training programmes for clinicians]	Yes

	The trainings are optional and the format and duration of the trainings are adapted to each need identified (not time-defined/periodic).
[Training programmes for patient advocates]	Uncertain
[Other (please specify)]	Yes
	The trainings are optional and the format and duration of the trainings are adapted to each need identified (not time-defined/periodic).
[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	
[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	Yes
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	Yes
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	Yes
[Monitoring and evaluation]	No
[Other]	<p>1) Infarmed (National Authority of Medicines and Health Products) – public consultation (regulatory, health technology assessment, pharmacovigilance, etc) and involvement with patient associations – Projeto INCLUIR (not exclusive for cancer - https://www.infarmed.pt/documents/15786/2304493/-Enquadramento+do+Projeto+INCLUIR/14ee5af7-743a-4f99-b463-ee78efd0a775?version=1.1)</p> <p>2) 2) DGS: 2.1) National Strategy includes 2 patient associations in the executive board, rotative model, to represent all patient associations. Participation in the strategy development long term. 2.2) National Cancer Hub (a co-joint initiative between the Directorate-General for Health and AICIB) includes Citizens and Patients Forum (exclusive) and Stakeholders Group</p>
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	Yes

	DGS – National Strategy includes 2 patient associations in the executive board Link to the Despacho (Annex – topic 2.1.): https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/despacho/13227-2023-835712442
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	Yes
	INFARMED – Consultive Board includes 2 patient associations (however, this is not specific for cancer) Link: https://www.infarmed.pt/web/infarmed/institucional-estrutura-e-organizacao/conselho-consultivo
[Other (please specify)]	No
[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	Yes
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	No
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	No
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	No
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	No
[Other]	No
[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	No
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	No
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	No
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	No
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	Yes
[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting,	

adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.	
[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]	Yes
	<p>1) DGS- there is a legal document (Aviso) of DGS that is a formal procedure that possibilities Patient and Public Involvement in the participation of the DGS documents/guidelines (through public consultation and proactive participation) – though applicable to oncology, this is not cancer specific. This document allows PPIE, however it is not at a key stage of oncology policy (it’s a wide range document, so not to be considered “key stage”) Reference: Aviso n.º 276/2015, de 9 de janeiro - “Artigo 4.º - Right to participate - The DGS promotes, whenever appropriate, public consultations on the documents it issues, publicizing the draft documents on its website or directly inviting specialists to give their opinions”</p> <p>2) DGS – through the national strategy executive board [https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/despacho/13227-2023-835712442], that is currently beginning its implementation and work, puts patients/citizens at the strategic board, participating in the agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation and evaluation of the national strategy.</p>
[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	No
[Cannot answer / not sure]	No
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	
<i>National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy</i>	
[15/16] Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	Yes
[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	2023
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[17] Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	Yes

[No]	No
[Other]	No
[18] If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	
[Patient Advocate]	No
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	Open public consultation (accordingly to the DGS SOP)
[19] To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	
[Not at all]	No
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	No
[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	No
[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	Yes
[Other]	No
[20] If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	
[Patient Advocate]	No
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	No
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	
<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	
[21] Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	No
[Plain language]	No
[Hybrid/remote]	No

[Stipends/expenses]	No
[Accessible venue/design]	No
[Childcare]	No
[Digital inclusion support]	No
[Cannot answer]	Yes
[Other]	No
[22/23] At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	No
[Specify the type of partnership]	-
[No]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	
<i>This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.</i>	
[24] Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	Yes
[Internal only]	No
[Public]	No
[Other]	No
[25] When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	
[Not published]	No
[Published (only summary)]	Yes
[Published with response]	No
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	No
[Other]	No
[26] Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	
[Published on the institution's official website]	Yes
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	No
[Published as a press release or news article]	No
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	No

[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	No
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	No
[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	No
[Not systematically made public]	No
[Other]	No
Area 4 -Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	
<i>This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology — from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.</i>	
<p>[27] To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)? 1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;</p>	
[Identifying priorities]	1
[Designing programmes/regulations]	1
[Collecting input/evidence]	2
[Analysing input/evidence]	2
[Communicating results]	2
[Implementing programmes]	4
[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	1
Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources	
<i>This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.</i>	
<p>[28] Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?</p>	
[None]	Yes
	there are no public resources allocated for their involvement, which may compromise their involvement and participation
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	No
[Funds for accompanying research]	No
[Funds for patient organisations]	No
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	No
[Other]	No
<p>[29/30] At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.</p>	

[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	No
[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	-
[No — no such policy exists]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	
<i>This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.</i>	
[31/33] Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	
[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	-
[Technical support]	-
[Funding schemes]	-
[Other]	-
[32] Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
Answer is “No”. There are no strengthen capacity initiatives, but rather attempts to engage and listen to needs, in order to work on a strategy for better patient/civilian involvement and empowerment (only isolated attempts).	
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	
<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	
[34/35] Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	No
[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	No
[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	Yes
[Don't know / Not applicable]	No
[Other]	No

[36] As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.

Collaboration between all the pentahelix sectors is considered key and are promoted (public administration (DGS-PNDO), National agencies (AICIB), Citizens and Civil Societies, Health and Care, Knowledge and academia, and Industry).

Romania

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	20
Date submitted	22.11.2025
General Questions	
[1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	INOMED
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	Rumania
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	No
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	No
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	Yes
[Other]	No
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	No
[Slightly important]	Yes
[Moderately important]	No
[Very important]	No
[Extremely important]	No
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	No
[Training programmes for clinicians]	No
[Training programmes for patient advocates]	No
[Other (please specify)]	No
[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	

[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	Yes
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	No
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	No
[Monitoring and evaluation]	No
[Other]	No
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	
[Yes]	No
[No]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	No
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	No
[Other (please specify)]	Yes
[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	N/A
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	N/A
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	N/A
[Other]	N/A
[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	N/A
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	N/A
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	N/A

[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	N/A
[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.	
[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]	No
[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	Yes
[Cannot answer / not sure]	No
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	
<i>National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy</i>	
[15/16] Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	Yes
[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	2022
[No]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
[17] Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Other]	No
[18] If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	
[Patient Advocate]	No
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	Yes
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	No
[19] To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	
[Not at all]	No
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	Yes

[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	No
[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	No
[Other]	No
[20] If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	
[Patient Advocate]	No
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	No
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	
<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	
[21] Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	No
[Plain language]	No
[Hybrid/remote]	No
[Stipends/expenses]	No
[Accessible venue/design]	No
[Childcare]	No
[Digital inclusion support]	No
[Cannot answer]	Yes
[Other]	No
[22/23] At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	No
[Specify the type of partnership]	-
[No]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	
<i>This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.</i>	

[24] Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	Yes
[Internal only]	No
[Public]	No
[Other]	No
[25] When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	
[Not published]	No
[Published (only summary)]	No
[Published with response]	No
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	No
[Other]	N/A
[26] Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	
[Published on the institution's official website]	Yes
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	No
[Published as a press release or news article]	No
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	No
[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	No
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	No
[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	No
[Not systematically made public]	No
[Other]	No
Area 4 -Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	
<i>This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology — from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.</i>	
[27] To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)? 1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;	
[Identifying priorities]	2
[Designing programmes/regulations]	2
[Collecting input/evidence]	2
[Analysing input/evidence]	1
[Communicating results]	2
[Implementing programmes]	2
[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	1

Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources	
<i>This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.</i>	
[28] Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?	
[None]	Yes
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	No
[Funds for accompanying research]	No
[Funds for patient organisations]	No
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	No
[Other]	No
[29/30] At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.	
[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	No
[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	-
[No — no such policy exists]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	
<i>This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.</i>	
[31/33] Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	
[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	-
[Technical support]	-
[Funding schemes]	-
[Other]	-
[32] Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
N/A	
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	
<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	

[34/35] Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	No
[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	No
[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	No
[Don't know / Not applicable]	No
[Other]	No
[36] As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.	
Knowledge and academia	

Slovakia

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	35
Date submitted	03.12.2025
General Questions	
[1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	National Oncology Institute
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	Slovensko
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	No
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	No
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	Yes
[Other]	No
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	No
[Slightly important]	No
[Moderately important]	Yes
[Very important]	No
[Extremely important]	No
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	No
[Training programmes for clinicians]	No
[Training programmes for patient advocates]	No
[Other (please specify)]	Yes
	The experts from the National Oncology Institute (NOI) provided lectures during national

	conferences for clinicians, researchers, patient advocates, patients, and policy makers on the importance of PPIE. Moreover, the NOI has organized the "Roundtable discussion: European comprehensive cancer center network and the voice of the patient in comprehensive cancer care in Slovakia" with international experts on PPIE at the Ministry of Health of the Slovak Republic. We have also participated in preparing the program and providing the lecture on the importance of patient voice in research, cancer care, and cancer policy making and decisions at the 1st conference for the patients and caregivers (Openly and Expertly about Cancer).
[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	
[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	Yes
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	Yes
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	No
[Monitoring and evaluation]	No
[Other]	No
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	No
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	Yes
	Patient Advisory Board at the Ministry of Health - it includes the representatives from different patient´s organizations not only those that are involved in the field of oncology
[Other (please specify)]	Yes
	Patient Council at the National Cancer Institute that is a national reference center for cancer care in Slovakia

[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	No
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	No
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	Yes
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	No
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	No
[Other]	there is a voting right of patient representatives in the process of including the new drugs in the list of reimbursed drugs by Insurance Companies, and there is also a formal working group for cancer screening awareness at the Ministry of Health where the relevant patient organizations are involved as regular members
[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	N/A
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	N/A
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	N/A
[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.	
[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]	No
[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	Yes
[Cannot answer / not sure]	No
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	

National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy

[15/16] Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	Yes
[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	2025
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[17] Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	No
[No]	Yes
[Other]	No
[18] If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	
[Patient Advocate]	N/A
[Patient Organization Representative]	N/A
[Patient Expert]	N/A
[Community Advocate]	N/A
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	N/A
[Public / Policy Expert]	N/A
[Other]	N/A
[19] To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	
[Not at all]	No
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	Yes
[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	No
[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	No
[Other]	We drafted the updated Action Plans for 2026-2030 with involvement of patient voice as advisory body.
[20] If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	
[Patient Advocate]	Yes
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No

[Civil Society Organization Representative]	No
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	No
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	
<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	
[21] Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	No
[Plain language]	Yes
[Hybrid/remote]	No
[Stipends/expenses]	No
[Accessible venue/design]	No
[Childcare]	No
[Digital inclusion support]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[Other]	No
[22/23] At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	Yes
[Specify the type of partnership]	Slovakia has a position called the Government Plenipotentiary for National Minorities, whose role is to represent and coordinate the interests of national minorities (narodnostnemensiny.vlada.gov.sk), including health issues.
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	
<i>This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.</i>	
[24] Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	No
[Internal only]	No
[Public]	Yes
[Other]	Annual Report on State of Oncology and Annual Report on State of Cancer Screening

	Programmes, as well as different working groups and the National Cancer Plan are publicly available at the webpage of the National Oncology Institute and the Ministry of Health of Slovak Republic.
[25] When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	
[Not published]	No
[Published (only summary)]	No
[Published with response]	No
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	No
[Other]	some events are published at the webpages or sometimes in the media (e.g. magazines, TV), and some events are only internally saved as the minutes.
[26] Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	
[Published on the institution's official website]	Yes
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	No
[Published as a press release or news article]	Yes
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	Yes
[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	Yes
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	Yes
[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	Yes
[Not systematically made public]	No
[Other]	No
Area 4 -Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	
<i>This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology — from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.</i>	
[27] To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)? 1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;	
[Identifying priorities]	2
[Designing programmes/regulations]	2
[Collecting input/evidence]	2
[Analysing input/evidence]	2
[Communicating results]	2
[Implementing programmes]	2

[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	2
Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources	
<i>This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.</i>	
[28] Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?	
[None]	Yes
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	No
[Funds for accompanying research]	No
[Funds for patient organisations]	No
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	No
[Other]	No
[29/30] At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.	
[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	No
[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	-
[No — no such policy exists]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	
<i>This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.</i>	
[31/33] Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	
[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	Yes, ad hoc initiatives only
[Technical support]	Yes, ad hoc initiatives only
[Funding schemes]	Yes, ad hoc initiatives only
[Other]	No
[32] Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
https://www.noisk.sk/about-us/international-cooperation/crane https://www.noisk.sk/about-us/we-publish https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100067786074029 https://www.onkokontrola.sk/	
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	

<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	
[34/35] Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	No
[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	Yes
	In the updated Action Plans for 2026-2030 of the National Oncology Programme these indicators are planned to be included for evaluation.
[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	No
[Don't know / Not applicable]	No
[Other]	Patient Council at the National Cancer Institute (NCI) report their activities on the webpage of the NCI.
[36] As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.	
AIFP in Slovakia (Association of the Innovative Pharmaceutical Industry), Professional Societies (e.g., Slovak Oncology Society), Academia - e.g., Universities, Research Institutions - e.g., Biomedical Research Center of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, Civil Societies -e.g., Cancer Research Foundation, Ombudsman, Patient Organizations, Ministry of Health, healthcare providers (e.g., Cancer centers, hospitals, outpatient clinics, general practitioners, radiologists, gastroenterologists, pneumologists, gynecologists, etc.).	

Sweden

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	40
Date submitted	05.12.2025
General Questions	
[1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	National Board of Health and Welfare
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	Sweden
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	No
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	No
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	No
[Other]	The Swedish health care system has a regional structure comprising of 21 regions. By national law the regions have an obligation to provide healthcare to its citizens on equal terms. To that end they have tax collection rights provided by the constitution (Instrument of Government).
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	No
[Slightly important]	No
[Moderately important]	No
[Very important]	Yes
[Extremely important]	No
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	Yes

	<p>The Swedish Regional Cancer Centres (RCC) have national working groups and care program committees, as well as national guidelines, that systematically incorporate patient participation. https://cancercentrum.se/inenglish.763.html</p> <p>Research clinics are also involved in the referral processes, which take place during four fixed referral periods each year. EUATI Sweden is a platform that brings together clinicians, researchers, and patient advocates. It offers optional training programs online as well as workshops, although the current level of expertise provided is limited. EUPATI has received governmental funding, but it remains uncertain whether this support will continue. Eupati.se</p>
[Training programmes for clinicians]	Yes
	<p>The RCC's has a policy for patient and family involvement, supported by introductory documents and mandatory online training for patient and relative representatives (PNR). Remuneration, scope of assignment, and conflict of interest declarations are regulated through national agreements. Recurring training and introductory sessions are voluntary but conducted under formal agreements.</p>
[Training programmes for patient advocates]	Yes
	<p>Comprehensive knowledge management and national consultation rounds openly include patient associations, with planned cancer mission hub-functions integrated into the updated strategy.</p>
[Other (please specify)]	Yes
[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	
[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	Yes
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	Yes
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	Yes
[Monitoring and evaluation]	Yes
[Other]	<p>PPIE is performed via patient councils at all regional cancer centres.</p>
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	

[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	Yes
	In each Regional Cancer Centre (RCC), patient and relative representatives (PNR) are included in guideline groups and advisory groups to both SALAR and the RCC. Their involvement is also reflected in the iPAAC Roadmap.
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	Yes
	Patient associations are involved through referral processes, for example in the newly updated Cancer Strategy, with the Minister of Health chairing the government's patient council.
[Other (please specify)]	Yes
	Patient council at Comprehensive Cancer Centres (there are 5 CCC's in Sweden, Sahlgrenska CCC coordinate patient council).
[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	No
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	No
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	No
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	No
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	No
[Other]	Consultation procedures in government investigations and policy documents include documented input from patient organizations. While patient representatives and civil society organizations do not have voting rights, their involvement is systematic, documented, and embedded in both RCC structures and government policy processes.

[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	No
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	No
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	No
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	Yes
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	No
[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.	
[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]	Yes
	Patient organizations participate in referral rounds (four fixed periods per year) for national oncology strategies and policy documents. Example: The updated Swedish Cancer Strategy explicitly included patient associations in its consultation process. (https://www.regeringen.se/informationsmaterial/-/2024/11/battre-tillsammans--forslag-till-en-uppdaterad-nationell-cancerstrategi/)
[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	No
[Cannot answer / not sure]	No
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	
<i>National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy</i>	
[15/16] Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	Yes
[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	2009
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No

[17] Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Other]	No
[18] If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	
[Patient Advocate]	Yes
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	Yes
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	Yes
[Public / Policy Expert]	Yes
[Other]	No
[19] To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	
[Not at all]	No
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	No
[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	Yes
[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	Yes
[Other]	At the time of writing, a National Cancer Mission Hub (NCMH) is being established in Sweden and will be launched in 2026 under the name SweCan. SweCan consists of a partnership in which approximately 65 partners form a general assembly. Of these 65 partners, an estimated 15 are patient associations and civil society organizations. In SweCan each partner has one vote.
[20] If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	
[Patient Advocate]	No
[Patient Organization Representative]	Yes
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	Yes
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	No
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	

<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	
[21] Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	No
[Plain language]	Yes
[Hybrid/remote]	Yes
[Stipends/expenses]	Yes
[Accessible venue/design]	No
[Childcare]	No
[Digital inclusion support]	Yes
[Cannot answer]	No
[Other]	No
[22/23] At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	Yes
[Specify the type of partnership]	Cooperation with patient organizations, PNR care process groups, screening development. Initiatives to reach groups in lower social / income and education levels. The National Board of Health and Welfare participate in "Järvaveckan". Järvaveckan is a major annual civic and political event in Stockholm, designed to bring together citizens, politicians, businesses, authorities, and civil society to discuss democracy, inclusion, and social issues.
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	
<i>This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.</i>	
[24] Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	No
[Internal only]	Yes
[Public]	Yes
[Other]	No
[25] When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	
[Not published]	No

[Published (only summary)]	Yes
[Published with response]	Yes
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	No
[Other]	No
[26] Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	
[Published on the institution's official website]	Yes
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	Yes
[Published as a press release or news article]	Yes
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	Yes
[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	Yes
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	Yes
[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	Yes
[Not systematically made public]	No
[Other]	No
Area 4 -Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	
<i>This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology — from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.</i>	
[27] To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)? 1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;	
[Identifying priorities]	3
[Designing programmes/regulations]	4
[Collecting input/evidence]	4
[Analysing input/evidence]	4
[Communicating results]	4
[Implementing programmes]	4
[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	3
Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources	
<i>This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.</i>	
[28] Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?	
[None]	No
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	Yes

	National funds and regional agreements provide financing for the RCC's national supportive roles and activities, including patient cooperation.
[Funds for accompanying research]	Yes
	Funding is provided through agreements covering competencies, knowledge, data collection, quality registers, and clinical trials.
[Funds for patient organisations]	Yes
	Regional funding supports local patient organizations, while national funding is allocated to national patient organizations.
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	Yes
	Governmental funding is provided through agreements covering, e.g., rehabilitation and palliative care. (https://cancercentrum.se/inenglish.763.html)
[Other]	No
[29/30] At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.	
[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	Yes
	Agreements on remuneration apply when participating in PNR (patient counselling groups). However, there is also an ongoing discussion regarding the fact that individuals on permanent sick leave are not permitted to receive any income.
[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	In line with RCC policy, patient and relative representatives are entitled to reimbursement of travel expenses and compensation for the time they dedicate to their assignments.
[No — no such policy exists]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	
<i>This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.</i>	
[31/33] Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	
[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	Yes, regular initiatives without formal policy basis
[Technical support]	Yes, regular initiatives without formal policy basis
[Funding schemes]	Yes, regular initiatives without formal policy basis

[Other]	Yes, regular initiatives without formal policy basis
	Education and training are provided internally by the patient organizations themselves, ensuring that representatives are well prepared for their roles. In addition, specialized training in funding and resource management is offered through external providers, such as GIVA Sweden, which supports capacity-building in civil society organizations.
[32] Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
	https://cancercentrum.se/inenglish.763.html
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	
<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	
[34/35] Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	Yes
	Outcomes are systematically tracked, yet structured changes do not always follow from the results. In other words, measurement alone does not consistently lead to improvement. Lead times are monitored, along with quality parameters in care processes, patient-reported experience measures (PREM) and patient-reported outcome measures (PROM). Compliance with treatment guidelines is also assessed, providing a comprehensive framework for evaluation, though the translation of these insights into practice remains a challenge.
[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	No
[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	No
[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	Yes
[Don't know / Not applicable]	No
[Other]	The patient organizations provide differing responses here, which is why two opposing answer options are given.

[36] As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.

The National Board of Health and Welfare collaborate daily with stakeholders from all sectors in the pentahelix, although a bit more frequently with representatives from the health care sector. Patient organisations report the following: RCCs (national and regional), urology and oncology clinics and organizations, as well as fellow patient cancer organizations. The Swedish Cancer Society, the Cancer Rehabilitation Fund, and rehabilitation centers. The pharmaceutical and medtech industry. Universities, reimbursement agencies, and the Medical Products Agency (MPA).

Turkey

SURVEY RESPONSE	
Response ID	43
Date submitted	15.12.2025
General Questions	
[1] Please note: Your contact details will only be used internally, for example if we need to follow up with you regarding this questionnaire. All responses will be anonymized, and results will be presented without any personal identifiers.	
[Please indicate the name of the organisation you are representing]	General Directorate of Public Health, MoH
[Please indicate which country you are representing]	Türkiye
Area 1 - Strengthen public sector capacities	
<i>This section looks at how public administrations enable patient and public involvement (PPIE). It covers the importance given to PPIE, available training opportunities, common barriers and facilitators, and the existence of formal structures, rules, or procedures to support participation</i>	
[2] Which of the following best describes the healthcare system in your country?	
[Tax-funded national health service (Beveridge model, e.g. UK, Spain, Italy)]	No
[Social health insurance system (Bismarck model, e.g. Germany, Austria, France)]	No
[Mixed system (elements of both taxation and insurance, e.g. many Central and Eastern European countries)]	Yes
[Other]	No
[3] In public administration, how important is patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) for policy and programme development within your country?	
[Not all important]	No
[Slightly important]	No
[Moderately important]	No
[Very important]	Yes
[Extremely important]	No
[4-8] For each of the following, please indicate whether publicly funded training opportunities on PPIE exist.	
[Training programmes for researchers]	Uncertain
[Training programmes for clinicians]	Uncertain
[Training programmes for patient advocates]	Uncertain
[Other (please specify)]	Uncertain
[9] In your country, at which stages does the involvement of the public and patients usually take place in oncology-related topics and activities?	

[Policy development (e.g. strategies, laws, regulations)]	No
[Programme or service design (e.g. health services, prevention initiatives)]	Yes
[Implementation of policies or programmes]	No
[Monitoring and evaluation]	No
[Other]	No
[10] Are the public and patients formally represented in national or regional advisory structures on oncology (e.g. steering committees, ministry advisory groups) in your country?	
[Yes]	No
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	Yes
[11] If yes, please specify at which level	
[National cancer steering committee (please specify purpose)]	No
[Ministry advisory groups (please specify for which topics)]	N/A
[Other (please specify)]	No
[12] For ministry advisory groups, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the citizens/patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	N/A
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	N/A
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	N/A
[Other]	No
[13] For national cancer steering committees, please indicate what type of rules exist in oncology-related advisory structures in your country, for the participation of the public, patients and their respective representatives (civil society organisations etc.)?	
[No rules or practices for PPIE representation exist]	N/A
[Ad hoc / informal inclusion only, without clear rules]	N/A
[Rules exist, but PPIE is consultative only (no structured influence)]	N/A
[Rules exist, with advisory role (systematic consultation, documented input, but no voting rights)]	N/A

[Rules exist, with co-decisive role (formal voting rights / shared decision-making)]	N/A
[14] In your country, are there SOPs (e.g. legal requirements, ministerial guidelines, or formal procedures) that require PPIE at key stages of oncology policy (agenda-setting, drafting, adoption, implementation, evaluation)? Examples might include mandatory consultation of patient organisations when drafting a National Cancer Plan, patient representation in cancer steering committees, or formal rules for including civil society in programme evaluations. Please provide examples if known.	
[Yes — please specify which SOPs and provide examples and sources]	No
[No — to my knowledge, no such SOPs exist]	No
[Cannot answer / not sure]	Yes
Area 1B - National Cancer Control Plans	
<i>National Cancer Control Plans (NCCPs) and National Cancer Strategy documents are specific policy documents and central planning tools in oncology across EU countries. By dedicating this sub-section to NCCPs, the questionnaire explores how the broader principles of Area 1 are applied in a concrete, national-level strategy</i>	
[15/16] Does your country currently have a National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or cancer strategy?	
[Yes]	Yes
[Indicate the year of the current NCCP]	2021
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	No
[17] Was the current/most recent National Cancer Control Plan (NCCP) or Cancer Strategy in your country developed together with patients and/or citizens?	
[Yes]	Yes
[No]	No
[Other]	No
[18] If yes: Which types of representatives were involved?	
[Patient Advocate]	No
[Patient Organization Representative]	No
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	Yes
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	No
[19] To what extent are patients and/or citizens involved in implementing the National Cancer Control Plan in your country (e.g. through participation in working groups, advisory boards, or task forces)?	
[Not at all]	No
[Occasionally / ad hoc]	Yes

[Regularly, but without structured rules (informal involvement)]	No
[Regularly, with structured representation (e.g., mandated patient representatives in working groups)]	No
[Other]	No
[20] If involved: Which types of representatives are involved in implementation?	
[Patient Advocate]	No
[Patient Organization Representative]	No
[Patient Expert]	No
[Community Advocate]	No
[Civil Society Organization Representative]	Yes
[Public / Policy Expert]	No
[Other]	No
Area 2 - Accessibility, Diversity and Inclusion	
<i>This section explores how PPIE activities ensure accessibility and inclusion — for example, through translation, plain language, hybrid or remote participation, reimbursement, digital inclusion, and collaboration with organisations representing underserved or underrepresented groups.</i>	
[21] Are accessibility standards systematically applied to PPIE activities within public administration frameworks?	
[Translation]	No
[Plain language]	No
[Hybrid/remote]	No
[Stipends/expenses]	No
[Accessible venue/design]	No
[Childcare]	No
[Digital inclusion support]	No
[Cannot answer]	Yes
[Other]	No
[22/23] At the public administration level, are there structured partnerships or outreach activities with organisations representing underserved and/or underrepresented groups? Choose only one of the following answers.	
[Yes]	No
[Specify the type of partnership]	-
[No]	No
[Cannot answer]	Yes
Area 3 - Participation influences transparent decisions	
<i>This section examines how public administrations ensure that participation is transparent. It asks whether the involvement of participants is monitored and reported, and how the results of public consultations are shared with the wider public.</i>	

[24] Is the representation of participants in activities organised by public administration monitored and publicly reported?	
[No]	No
[Internal only]	No
[Public]	Yes
[Other]	No
[25] When your organisation conducts public consultations in the field of cancer policy, how are the results made publicly available?	
[Not published]	No
[Published (only summary)]	No
[Published with response]	Yes
[Published with response + audit/appeal]	No
[Other]	No
[26] Please specify how consultation outcomes are shared	
[Published on the institution's official website]	Yes
[Included in official policy or strategy reports]	Yes
[Published as a press release or news article]	Yes
[Communicated directly to participants or stakeholder organisations]	Yes
[Presented at public events, workshops, or conferences]	Yes
[Shared through social media or newsletters]	Yes
[Submitted to the Ministry of Health or other public bodies]	Yes
[Not systematically made public]	No
[Other]	No
Area 4 -Active mechanisms in Policy/Legislation development	
<i>This section explores how participation is embedded at different stages of policy and programme development in oncology — from setting priorities to implementation and evaluation— and the level of involvement at each stage.</i>	
[27] To what extent are patients and the public involved in different phases of policy or programme development in the field of oncology (from prevention to quality of life)? 1=No involvement; 2=Ad hoc or informal involvement; 3=Structured consultation (occasional input); 4=Regular consultation or advisory participation; 5=Co-decision or institutionalised involvement;	
[Identifying priorities]	N/A
[Designing programmes/regulations]	N/A
[Collecting input/evidence]	N/A
[Analysing input/evidence]	N/A
[Communicating results]	N/A
[Implementing programmes]	N/A
[Monitoring & evaluation of outcomes]	N/A

Area 5 – Adequate and sustainable resources	
<i>This section addresses the resources available to support PPIE, such as funding, staff, and technical support. It also covers policies on remuneration or reimbursement for patient and public contributors, and whether regulations or guidelines exist.</i>	
[28] Are there sustainable public sector resources (e.g. budget, staff, technical support) allocated to ensure effective PPIE in oncology related activities?	
[None]	Yes
[Funds for support facilities (e.g. competence center participation)]	-
[Funds for accompanying research]	No
[Funds for patient organisations]	No
[Funds for expense allowances or similar]	No
[Other]	No
[29/30] At the national or regional level, is there a policy on remuneration or reimbursement for patient or public contributors (e.g. fees, travel costs, time compensation)? Please note that details provided in the text box will be valuable for data validation and analysis.	
[Yes — please specify and provide details in the text box]	No
[Are there any related regulations or guidelines? Please describe what type.]	-
[No — no such policy exists]	No
[Cannot answer]	Yes
Area 6 - Civil Society Capacity Strengthening	
<i>This section looks at initiatives that help civil society and patient organisations participate effectively. It includes training, technical support, and funding schemes, and whether these are regular and supported by policy or only occasional.</i>	
[31/33] Are there initiatives to strengthen the capacity of civil society and patient organisations for effective participation (e.g. training, technical support, funding schemes)?	
[Trainings (e.g., public administration staff)]	N/A
[Technical support]	N/A
[Funding schemes]	N/A
[Other]	N/A
	No answer
[32] Please provide additional information regarding your previous answers (e.g. links, resources, or further explanations).	
No answer	
Area 7 - Monitoring and Evaluation	
<i>Area 7 examines whether organisations track and report outcomes that link PPIE activities to decision-making processes.</i>	

[34/35] Does your organisation (or affiliated entities) track and report outcome indicators that link patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) to decision-making (e.g. policy changes, resource allocation, improved access or uptake, equity impacts)?	
[Yes, outcome indicators are systematically tracked and reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are tracked but not systematically reported]	No
[Yes, outcome indicators are occasionally tracked or reported on an ad hoc basis]	No
[No, but development of such indicators is planned]	No
[No, such indicators are not currently tracked or reported]	No
[Don't know / Not applicable]	Yes
[Other]	No
[36] As part of your daily work, which stakeholders from other sectors do you collaborate with most on oncology-related activities? Please consider the following sectors: Health and Care, Knowledge and Academia, Citizens and Civil Society, and Industry.	
Academia, Civil Society, Related Ministries	